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Empowering Change Through Raizal Perspectives on Prison Education in San Andrés Island

Sigifredo Castell Britton
Walden University

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Walden University

College of Psychology and Community Services

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Sigifredo Castell Britton

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Walden University
2024

Abstract

Empowering Change Through Raizal Perspectives on Prison Education in San Andrés

Island

by

Sigifredo Castell Britton

Dissertation Submitted in Partial Fulfillment

of the Requirements for the Degree of

Doctor of Philosophy

Criminal Justice

Walden University

November 2024

Abstract

Raizal ex-offenders on San Andrés Island, Colombia, encounter significant challenges when reintegrating into their community, often compounded by ineffective prison education programs and the unique sociocultural dynamics of the Raizal community. While previous researchers have identified barriers to successful reintegration, a deeper understanding of the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and the perspectives of community leaders is needed. This phenomenological study, guided by culturally responsive pedagogy and social disorganization theory, was conducted to explore these experiences and perspectives. Through semistructured interviews with 10 Raizal ex-offenders and 10 community leaders, data were collected to examine the effectiveness of current prison education programs and the impact of overpopulation and cultural erosion on the reintegration process. Thematic coding of the data revealed key themes: (a) inadequate prison education, (b) lack of cultural relevance in educational content, (c) consideration of returning to crime, and (d) broader socioeconomic challenges such as overpopulation and government corruption. Findings demonstrate existing prison education programs fail to meet the cultural needs of Raizal inmates, contributing to high recidivism rates and reintegration difficulties. The findings from this study can lead to positive social change by informing policymakers and practitioners of the critical need for culturally responsive prison education programs and helping in the development of reforms to support successful reintegration, thereby contributing to positive social change.

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Dedication

To the Raizal people of San Andrés, Old Providence, and Santa Catalina Islands and of the Cayman Islands. This study is dedicated to you. May the findings here serve as a spark for dialogue and collaboration. The rich cultural heritage and resilience of both island communities offer valuable lessons for one another. By fostering understanding and exchange, San Andrés and the Cayman Islands can continue to thrive as unique cultural hubs within the Caribbean.

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Chapter 1: Introduction to the Study

Introduction

The surge in the global population in recent decades has brought significant challenges, particularly in densely populated areas (United Nations, 2023). San Andrés Island, Colombia, a tourist destination in the Caribbean, presents a microcosm of these population-related challenges. The island struggles with overpopulation that strains resources and exacerbates social and economic pressures (Bullard, 2018). The Raizal people, the island's indigenous Afro-Caribbean community with a distinct cultural heritage, are disproportionately affected by these pressures (Archbold, 2019). This situation creates a breeding ground for a potential cycle of crime and incarceration, further burdening the already overcrowded prison system. The Raizal community's unique cultural identity may leave them particularly vulnerable to these challenges.

This chapter includes an introduction to this research study on the potential of culturally relevant education programs to reduce recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders on San Andrés Island. The following sections are included in this chapter: background, problem statement, purpose of the study, research questions, theoretical framework, nature of the study, definitions, assumptions, scope and delimitations, limitations, and significance of the study. The chapter concludes with a summary of the most important and relevant information about this research study.

Background

San Andrés Island, located in the Caribbean Sea approximately 775 kilometers northwest of mainland Colombia, is part of the San Andrés, Providencia, and Santa

Catalina archipelago. The island is positioned near Nicaragua and is the largest island in the archipelago. San Andrés, with its diverse ecosystems and rich cultural heritage, serves as a unique sociocultural and geopolitical entity in the Caribbean. The island's total area is about 26 square kilometers, and it is home to a unique blend of cultures, with the Raizal people forming a significant portion of the population.

Historical Context and Cultural Heritage

The history of San Andrés Island is marked by its colonial past and the struggles of the Raizal community, an Afro-Caribbean population with a distinct cultural heritage. The Raizal people have long maintained a unique cultural identity, including their Creole language, traditional music, and religious practices, distinct from mainland Colombian culture. Historically, the Raizals have faced challenges in preserving their cultural identity, particularly as the island has experienced increasing waves of immigration from mainland Colombia, creating tensions over land, resources, and cultural preservation (Hooker, 2005).

During the 17th and 18th centuries, San Andrés was a haven for English settlers, pirates, and privateers and later became a hub for the slave trade. The Raizal community emerged from these early Afro-descendant populations and has continued to inhabit the island, retaining a strong sense of cultural autonomy and self-determination despite external pressures from colonial and postcolonial powers (Aldrich & Connell, 2020). This unique cultural and historical context has shaped the sociopolitical landscape of the island and the experiences of its inhabitants.

Socioeconomic Conditions and Overpopulation

San Andrés Island, a part of Colombia's Caribbean archipelago, is currently one of the most densely populated islands in the Caribbean, with a population exceeding 100,000 residents on a landmass of just 26 square kilometers. This population density is driven by natural growth and a significant influx of mainland Colombians, leading to profound socioeconomic pressures that have strained the island's infrastructure, resources, and social services (Bullard, 2018). These challenges have resulted in heightened tensions between the native Raizal community and newer arrivals, often manifesting in land disputes, competition for employment, and environmental degradation, which has deteriorated the quality of life for many residents.

The Raizal people, indigenous to San Andrés, have historically relied on the island's natural resources and community-centered economic systems. Overpopulation, however, has intensified problems such as unemployment and underemployment within the Raizal community, reducing their access to adequate housing, healthcare, and education (Archbold, 2019). This marginalization is further exacerbated by policies favoring mainland Colombians, who are perceived to have greater economic and political influence (Moreno, 2019). The social exclusion of the Raizal community is reflected in the high incarceration rates among Raizal individuals, underscoring the urgent need for culturally sensitive and responsive approaches to reduce recidivism and promote community reintegration.

Recent studies by Castell-Britton (2024) highlight that the high crime rates in San Andrés are directly linked to the island's overpopulation and its socioeconomic

instability. The island's strategic location has made it a hub for drug trafficking and other illegal activities, contributing to rising crime rates, including homicides, robberies, and drug-related offenses. This criminal activity is compounded by the presence of organized crime groups such as the Gaitanist Self-Defense Forces of Colombia and remnants of the Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia. Overpopulation has created an environment where law enforcement is stretched thin, and community resources are insufficient to manage the escalating violence and insecurity (InSight Crime, 2023). The combination of overpopulation and socioeconomic marginalization contributes to a cycle of crime and incarceration, particularly among the island's Raizal community, who often lack the necessary support systems for successful rehabilitation and reintegration.

Castell-Britton's research also reveals that overpopulation has led to the deterioration of living conditions, with limited access to essential services such as clean water, adequate healthcare, and education, further intensifying social and economic disparities. The ongoing competition for scarce resources between the Raizal community and new arrivals from mainland Colombia has created a precarious sociopolitical environment, where the Raizal community's cultural identity and economic stability are under threat. Addressing these issues requires a comprehensive approach that includes culturally relevant education programs and community-based support to reduce recidivism and foster sustainable development on the island.

Challenges Faced by Incarcerated Raizal Individuals

Incarcerated individuals from minority communities, including the Raizal people, face unique challenges within the prison system. These challenges include cultural

isolation, a lack of culturally relevant resources, and limited opportunities for effective rehabilitation (Bergman, 2020). For the Raizal community, the experience of incarceration often involves a disconnect from their cultural roots and values, which are critical for identity and rehabilitation. The absence of programs that address these unique cultural needs can make reintegration into society particularly difficult, increasing the likelihood of recidivism.

The high rates of incarceration among the Raizal community are indicative of broader systemic issues, including limited access to justice and biased law enforcement practices (Cruz & Torrejano, 2020). This has led to a cycle in which individuals are released from prison without the necessary support or resources to successfully reintegrate, often resulting in reoffending and reincarceration. Thus, there is a critical need for interventions that are both effective and culturally sensitive to address the complex challenges faced by Raizal ex-offenders.

Potential of Culturally Relevant Education Programs

Culturally relevant education programs have emerged as a promising approach to address the specific needs of underrepresented communities within correctional settings. These programs are designed to be responsive to the cultural backgrounds, experiences, and learning styles of the target population (Gay, 2018). Research indicates that such programs offer numerous benefits by fostering a sense of belonging, increasing engagement and motivation, and promoting self-efficacy. For the Raizal community, culturally relevant education programs could be an essential tool for rehabilitation, helping to bridge the gap between the prison environment and their cultural context.

Ladson-Billings (1995) demonstrated the positive impact of culturally responsive education on students' sense of community and inclusion. Learning experiences that connect with students' cultural backgrounds tend to be more engaging and motivating. Content that is relevant to students' lives and experiences captures their interest and encourages active participation, leading to better academic performance and sustained enthusiasm for learning (Gay, 2018). This approach is particularly relevant in correctional education, where fostering a sense of belonging and community can significantly impact recidivism rates.

Empowerment Through Culturally Relevant Education

Additionally, culturally relevant education programs empower individuals by validating their cultural identities and leveraging their unique strengths. These programs acknowledge and build upon the cultural assets that students bring to the learning environment, fostering a sense of self-efficacy. Bandura (1997) described self-efficacy as one's belief in their ability to succeed in specific situations, which is crucial for personal and academic growth. For the Raizal people, programs that validate their cultural heritage and provide practical skills aligned with local economic opportunities can play a vital role in their successful reintegration (Courtney, 2023).

Research continues to affirm the importance of culturally relevant education in enhancing students' self-efficacy and overall success (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). In the context of correctional education, these programs can provide a critical bridge between institutional education and real-world applications, thereby aiding in successful reintegration into society (Chang & Viesca, 2022; Rogers, 2021). For the Raizal

community, whose socioeconomic challenges are deeply intertwined with their cultural identity, culturally relevant education programs can help address these complexities more effectively (Cabrera et al., 2021).

Gap in Knowledge and Need for the Study

Research suggests the potential benefits of culturally relevant education programs in reducing recidivism (e.g., Petersilia, 2022). However, there is a specific gap in knowledge regarding the implementation and long-term impact of these programs for the Raizal people of San Andrés. The Raizal people, an underrepresented community with a distinct cultural heritage, face unique challenges within the San Andrés prison system. While existing research highlights the general challenges faced by minority communities in prison (Bergman, 2020), there is a lack of recent studies specifically examining the effectiveness of culturally relevant education programs designed for the Raizal community. Ladson-Billings (1995) emphasized the importance of tailoring educational interventions to specific cultural contexts, further highlighting this knowledge gap.

This study aimed to address this gap through an investigation of the implementation and impact of culturally relevant education programs for the Raizal people incarcerated in San Andrés. Examining the program design, delivery methods, and long-term outcomes for participants has provided valuable insights into the effectiveness of this approach in reducing recidivism rates and promoting positive change within this specific marginalized community. Additionally, the study contributes to the broader field of correctional education by offering evidence-based recommendations for developing and implementing culturally relevant educational programs.

Problem Statement

The situation that prompted this research is the recognition, while prison education programs hold promise in reducing recidivism rates (Davis et al., 2013), the overpopulation crisis on San Andrés Island significantly strains resources and infrastructure (Cruz & Torrejano, 2020). This strain exacerbates social and economic disparities, potentially contributing to higher crime rates (Archbold, 2019). Consequently, the effectiveness of existing prison education programs, particularly in addressing the specific cultural needs of the Raizal ex-offender community, is likely hindered. There is a critical gap in research focused on developing and implementing culturally responsive education programs specifically designed for the Raizal community. Addressing this gap holds the potential to lower recidivism rates.

Despite the well-documented benefits of prison education programs in reducing recidivism, a crucial gap persists; existing studies often overlook the critical role of cultural context in the effectiveness of these programs (Ladson-Billings, 1995). This study transcends this limitation by focusing specifically on the Raizal population on San Andrés Island, Colombia. By delving into the lived experiences and cultural background of Raizal ex-offenders, this research offers a unique perspective that could yield valuable insights for developing more effective and culturally responsive education programs.

The specific research problem addressed through this study is the gap in knowledge regarding how existing prison education programs on San Andrés Island function in addressing recidivism among the Raizal ex-offender population. Current prison education programs may not adequately consider the Raizal cultural context,

which can hinder successful reintegration and contribute to higher recidivism rates. There is limited understanding of how culturally responsive educational programs can be designed and implemented to meet the unique needs of the Raizal community. Existing research highlights the general challenges faced by marginalized communities in prison (Bergman, 2020), but there is a lack of studies that specifically examine the effectiveness of culturally relevant education programs for the Raizal community.

Investigating the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders and Raizal community leaders through a qualitative approach, I conducted this research to develop a culturally relevant educational program that fosters positive change and successful reintegration within the Raizal community. This study is particularly relevant to the discipline of criminal justice and correctional education, as it addresses the critical issue of recidivism reduction through culturally tailored interventions. The findings provide a robust evidence base for the development and implementation of more effective and culturally sensitive educational programs, ultimately contributing to lower recidivism rates and improving social outcomes for the Raizal community on San Andrés Island.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study was to explore the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders regarding the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and to identify opportunities for developing culturally relevant programs that can reduce recidivism rates and promote successful reintegration into the Raizal community on San Andrés Island. The theoretical significance of the study lay in its application of culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP) and social

disorganization theory (SDT) within the specific context of the Raizal community's correctional education. The findings expand these theoretical frameworks by providing insights into the role of cultural relevance in educational interventions for marginalized populations.

The practical significance of the study is in proposing solutions to the challenges faced by Raizal ex-offenders in their reintegration process. Based on the findings, the study aims to offer evidence-based recommendations for developing culturally responsive prison education programs. The results of this research can be instrumental in helping policymakers, educators, and criminal justice practitioners design and implement effective interventions that address the unique needs of the Raizal community, ultimately contributing to reduced recidivism and successful reintegration of ex-offenders.

Research Questions

The research questions (RQs) that guided the study were:

RQ1: What are the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders concerning the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and their impact on recidivism?

RQ2: What are the perspectives of Raizal community leaders concerning the challenges associated with the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders into the Raizal community postincarceration?

Theoretical Framework for the Study

The theories that grounded this study included SDT (Shaw & McKay, 1942) and CRP (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). SDT provides a framework for understanding how the breakdown of social institutions within a community can lead to various social

issues, including educational disparities. CRP emphasizes the importance of incorporating students' cultural backgrounds into teaching practices to enhance learning outcomes. This combined approach allowed for a comprehensive examination of the complex issue of education program effectiveness within the Raizal community by both the structural challenges and the need for culturally responsive educational strategies.

The logical connections between the frameworks of SDT and CRP and the nature of this study are crucial for examining the research problem from multiple perspectives. SDT provides a foundation for understanding the social dynamics within the Raizal community, identifying factors that may contribute to recidivism. CRP, on the other hand, allows for an in-depth exploration of how culturally responsive education programs can mitigate these challenges by addressing the specific cultural needs of the Raizal population. By integrating these frameworks, the study can offer a comprehensive lens through which to understand the multifaceted issues at play.

Qualitative research methods are well-suited to both SDT and CRP. Through semistructured interviews with key Raizal stakeholders, including ex-offenders and community leaders, I delved into lived experiences and perspectives, providing rich insights into the complex interplay between social bonds, decision making in education, and the effectiveness of existing programs within the Raizal community. By employing these theoretical frameworks alongside a qualitative approach, I aimed to bridge the gap in knowledge regarding the functionality of current prison education programs on San Andrés Island and their effectiveness in addressing recidivism among the Raizal ex-

offender population. This integration of theory and method enhances the study's ability to generate a nuanced understanding of the research problem.

Nature of the Study

Rationale for Selection of the Design, Paradigm, and Tradition

In this qualitative study, I employed a phenomenological approach to explore the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders on San Andrés Island, Colombia, concerning prison education programs, recidivism, and reintegration (see Creswell & Poth, 2018). A phenomenological design was chosen to focus on understanding how individuals perceive and made sense of their lived experiences. This method was particularly appropriate for this study as it allowed for an in-depth exploration of the subjective meanings that participants attach to their experiences, providing valuable insights into how they navigate the complexities of prison education, cultural identity, and reintegration processes. The phenomenological approach aligned with the study's aim to uncover the cultural relevance and effectiveness of prison education programs within the unique sociocultural context of the Raizal community.

Key Concept and Phenomenon Being Investigated

The central concept investigated in this study was the effectiveness of prison education programs in reducing recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders. The phenomenon of interest was the lived experiences and perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders regarding these programs, particularly within the cultural context of the Raizal community. I sought to understand how these educational programs impact recidivism rates and the reintegration process, considering the unique cultural needs,

values, and backgrounds of the Raizal people. By focusing on these lived experiences, I aimed to highlight the cultural dimensions that influence the effectiveness of such programs and the broader implications for social reintegration.

Summary of the Methodology

To gather rich, detailed data that align with the phenomenological approach, I employed semistructured interviews. This method allowed for flexibility and ensured consistency across interviews. A tailored interview guide was developed for each stakeholder group (Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders) to capture their unique perspectives (Creswell & Poth, 2018). The interview guide also allowed for exploring unexpected insights that emerged during conversations, further enriching the data and understanding of the phenomenon under study (see Stake, 2020).

Data collection involved recruiting participants through purposive sampling to guarantee those interviewed had relevant experiences and insights into the research questions. The interviews were conducted in a conversational manner, allowing participants to share their stories and experiences in their own words. The data were analyzed using thematic coding to identify recurring themes and patterns related to the effectiveness and cultural relevance of prison education programs.

Definitions

These are the definitions for the key terms used in this study:

Community leaders: The Raizals who are involved in positive change within the archipelago of San Andrés, Providencia, and Santa Catalina. This includes teachers, doctors, police officers, religious pastors, businesspeople, and every person who takes an

active role in being a role model for children and teenagers. These individuals are characterized by their good character and can be considered justices of the peace. They are recognized as leaders due to their excellent service and dedication to their community.

Culturally responsive pedagogy (CRP): An educational approach that acknowledges and values the cultural backgrounds, knowledge systems, and learning styles of students, aiming to create an inclusive and engaging learning environment (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995).

Interpretivist paradigm: Emphasizes understanding the subjective meanings individuals attach to their experiences and the social world around them. This approach focuses on qualitative research methods like interviews and observations to gain insights into lived experiences and perspectives (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018).

Purposive sampling: A sampling technique that involves selecting participants with specific characteristics or experiences relevant to the research question. This method ensures that the sample is representative of the population being studied, providing valuable insights into the research topic (Robinson, 2023).

Raizal people: An ethnic group with African and Indigenous Caribbean heritage, native to the archipelago of San Andrés, Providencia, and Santa Catalina, off Colombia's Caribbean coast. They possess a distinct cultural identity shaped by their history, language (San Andrés-Providencia Creole), and religious traditions (Arnaiz-Castro, Gómez-Parra, & Espejo-Mohedano, 2022).

Recidivism: The tendency of previously incarcerated individuals to relapse into criminal behavior, particularly after having been imprisoned. In this study, recidivism specifically pertains to the rate at which Raizal ex-offenders return to prison following their release (Davis et al., 2013; Duwe & Clark, 2017; Esperian, 2021).

Semistructured interviews: A qualitative data collection method that uses a predetermined interview guide with open-ended questions, allowing for flexibility and in-depth exploration of participants' experiences. This approach balances obtaining specific data with allowing participants to share their unique perspectives (Creswell, 2014).

Social disorganization theory (SDT): A theory positing that crime rates are higher in communities with weak social bonds and low levels of informal social control. This theory suggests that factors like poverty, unemployment, and residential instability contribute to a breakdown in social order, leading to increased crime (Shaw & McKay, 1942).

Thematic coding: A qualitative data analysis technique that involves identifying, categorizing, and analyzing recurring themes and patterns within data sets. This method allows researchers to make sense of qualitative data and identify key concepts that emerge from the collected information (Braun & Clarke, 2022).

Assumptions

In conducting this study, several assumptions were made that were critical to the research's meaningfulness. These assumptions, while believed to be true, cannot be empirically demonstrated within the scope of this research. I assumed the participants, including Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders, would provide honest and

reflective responses during the interviews. This assumption was necessary because the validity of the data collected depends on the authenticity and accuracy of the participants' accounts of their experiences with prison education programs and recidivism. I aimed to explore the lived experiences and perceptions of the participants, which required truthful and detailed accounts. Without honest responses, the findings would be skewed, leading to inaccurate conclusions.

Furthermore, I assumed culturally relevant educational programs could positively influence the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders and reduce recidivism rates. This assumption was based on existing literature that suggests CRP enhances student engagement, motivation, and self-efficacy (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). Applying this assumption to the Raizal context was necessary to explore the potential benefits of culturally tailored educational interventions. Additionally, I assumed Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders would be willing to participate in the study and share their experiences and insights. The study's success depended on the participation of individuals who had firsthand knowledge and experience of the prison education programs and the challenges faced by the Raizal community. Willing participation was essential to gather comprehensive and meaningful data.

Aligned with the interpretivist paradigm, I assumed knowledge was constructed through interaction and that understanding the subjective meanings individuals attach to their experiences was crucial (Denzin & Lincoln, 2018). This assumption aligned with the interpretivist paradigm, which underpins the phenomenological approach used in this study. It was necessary to accept this paradigm to justify the use of qualitative methods

and the emphasis on participants' lived experiences. Moreover, I assumed the findings from this study, while specific to the Raizal community on San Andrés Island, could provide insights applicable to similar minority communities in other contexts. This assumption was necessary to extend the implications of the study beyond the immediate context, contributing to the broader field of correctional education and recidivism reduction among minority populations. Finally, I assumed the social and economic conditions affecting the Raizal community on San Andrés Island would remain relatively stable during the study period. Consistent social conditions were necessary to ensure that changes in recidivism rates or perceptions of educational programs were not unduly influenced by external factors. This stability allowed for a clearer analysis of the impact of the educational interventions being studied.

Scope and Delimitations

This study was conducted to specifically address the effectiveness of existing prison education programs in reducing recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders on San Andrés Island and to explore opportunities for developing culturally relevant programs. The focus was chosen due to the unique socioeconomic and cultural challenges faced by the Raizal community, which are not adequately addressed by the educational interventions within the prison system. Through the exploration of the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders, I aimed to identify the specific needs and cultural elements that could have enhanced the effectiveness of prison education programs.

To ensure a focused and relevant investigation, I established clear boundaries regarding the populations included and the perspectives sought. These boundaries were essential for maintaining the integrity and specificity of the research. The primary population in this study included Raizal individuals who had been incarcerated and were in the process of reintegrating into society. This focus enabled an in-depth understanding of how culturally relevant education programs influenced their reintegration experiences and reduced recidivism rates (Courtney, 2023). Additionally, key figures within the Raizal community who possessed insight into the cultural and social dynamics of the population were included. These were religious pastors, medical doctors, teachers, police officers, and different leaders who had positively impacted their community. These community leaders provided valuable perspectives on the effectiveness and cultural relevance of educational programs tailored to Raizal ex-offenders (Ragoonaden & Müller, 2017).

The study excluded several groups to maintain its focus on the specific cultural context of the Raizal community. Non-Raizal ex-offenders, or individuals from other cultural or ethnic backgrounds who had been incarcerated but were not part of the Raizal community, were excluded to ensure the research remained specific to the Raizal context. General prison staff were also excluded, as their perspectives, while potentially valuable, do not directly align with the study's focus on the cultural relevance of educational programs for Raizal inmates. Finally, members of the Raizal community who were not actively involved in community improvement or did not serve as role models were not

included, as the study aimed to gather insights from those who had a significant and positive impact on their community.

In the pursuit of understanding the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders on prison education programs and reintegration challenges, this study was focused on specific theoretical frameworks while excluding others that could have provided additional perspectives. For example, I did not explore other criminological theories, such as strain theory or labeling theory, despite their potential to offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of prison education programs and reintegration processes. The decision to exclude these theories was made to maintain a concentrated focus on CRP and SDT, which were considered most relevant to the research objectives.

Additionally, I omitted broader educational frameworks that did not specifically address cultural responsiveness or the social context of crime. General educational theories that lacked a direct connection to the unique cultural and social challenges faced by the Raizal community were not included. By narrowing the theoretical scope in this way, the study aimed to provide a more in-depth analysis of how culturally responsive education programs and social dynamics specifically impact the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders.

Potential Transferability

While the findings of this study are specific to the Raizal community on San Andrés Island, they may have broader implications for other marginalized communities facing similar challenges within correctional systems. The insights gained from this research could be adapted and applied to develop culturally relevant education programs

in different sociocultural contexts. However, the transferability of the findings should be approached with caution, as cultural nuances and specific local conditions play a significant role in the effectiveness of such programs. Further research would be necessary to test the applicability of the findings in other settings.

Limitations

Design and Methodological Weaknesses

This study had several designs and methodological weaknesses that must be acknowledged. The reliance on self-reported data from interviews may have introduced bias, as participants might have provided socially desirable responses or might not have accurately recalled past experiences. Additionally, the purposive sampling method, while ensuring relevant participant selection, may have limited the generalizability of the findings to the broader Raizal population or other communities. The qualitative nature of the study, while rich in depth and detail, may have lacked the ability to establish causality or generalizable patterns across larger populations. Moreover, the potential influence of researcher bias in interpreting and analyzing qualitative data must be considered, despite efforts to mitigate this through rigorous coding and validation processes.

One significant limitation of this study is its transferability. The findings are specific to the Raizal community on San Andrés Island and may not be directly transferable to other contexts or minority groups. While the study aimed to provide detailed insights into the cultural context of the Raizal community, I acknowledge the need for further research to test the applicability of these findings in different settings. To

address this, detailed descriptions of the context and participants are provided to allow for better judgment of transferability.

As a qualitative study, the findings may have been influenced by the subjective interpretations of both the participants and the researcher, potentially affecting the dependability of the results (Creswell & Poth, 2018). To enhance dependability, a clear and consistent methodological approach was followed, including the use of semistructured interview guides and systematic coding procedures. Additionally, member checking was employed, allowing participants to review and confirm the accuracy of their interview transcripts.

Biases and Measures to Address Them

In conducting this study, various biases may have arisen that could have affected the accuracy and reliability of the findings. To ensure the integrity of the research, several measures were implemented to address and mitigate these biases.

Researchers' backgrounds, beliefs, and expectations could have influenced the data collection and interpretation process, leading to potential biases in the findings (see Maxwell, 2013). To address this, reflexivity was practiced throughout the study. I maintained a reflective journal to document personal biases and their potential impact on the research process. Regular peer debriefing sessions were also conducted to provide external checks on the research process and interpretations (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Participants may have provided socially desirable responses or may not have fully disclosed their experiences due to fear of judgment or repercussions. To mitigate this, participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses.

Interviews were conducted in a neutral and comfortable environment to encourage openness and honesty. Additionally, building rapport with participants before the interviews helped in gaining their trust and obtaining more genuine responses.

Reasonable Measures to Address Limitations

To address these limitations, several measures were implemented. Firstly, data triangulation was used by collecting information from multiple sources, including Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders. This approach helped to validate the findings and provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem. Secondly, providing rich, detailed descriptions of the research context, participants, and findings helped in assessing the transferability of the study. By offering a thorough account of the setting and the experiences of the participants, readers could better judge the applicability of the findings to other contexts. Lastly, maintaining a detailed audit trail of all research activities, decisions, and changes made during the study enhanced the transparency and dependability of the research. This included documenting the data collection and analysis processes, as well as any methodological adjustments.

Significance

This study was conducted to advance knowledge in the discipline of criminal justice and correctional education by providing empirical evidence on the effectiveness of culturally relevant education programs in reducing recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders. The theoretical frameworks of CRP and SDT were extended by being applied to a unique cultural context, offering insights into how cultural responsiveness could enhance educational outcomes in correctional settings. This research fills a critical gap in

the literature by focusing specifically on the Raizal community, a marginalized group that had been underrepresented in previous studies on prison education and recidivism.

The findings of this study have the potential to inform the development and implementation of prison education programs that are culturally tailored to the needs of minority communities (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). By highlighting the specific educational needs and cultural contexts of the Raizal community, this research could guide policymakers, educators, and correctional administrators in designing programs that are more effective in promoting reintegration and reducing recidivism (see Bergman, 2020). The study's recommendations could contribute to creating curricula that respect and incorporate the cultural heritage of the Raizal people, thus improving the overall quality and relevance of prison education programs (Ladson-Billings, 1995).

The study's implications for positive social change are significant and align with its scope. By developing and implementing culturally responsive education programs, the research aimed to reduce recidivism rates among Raizal ex-offenders, thereby facilitating their successful reintegration into society (Petersilia, 2022). This approach could lead to several positive social outcomes. First, culturally relevant education programs could foster a sense of belonging and community among Raizal ex-offenders, reducing feelings of isolation and marginalization (Courtney, 2023).

Additionally, lower recidivism rates could contribute to overall reductions in crime, thereby enhancing public safety and community well-being on San Andrés Island (Petersilia, 2022). Furthermore, the successful reintegration of ex-offenders could improve employment prospects and economic stability for individuals and their families,

thus contributing to the socioeconomic development of the Raizal community (Petersilia, 2022). Finally, the study's findings have the potential to influence policy at both local and national levels, encouraging the adoption of culturally responsive approaches in other marginalized communities and correctional systems, thereby promoting more inclusive and equitable criminal justice practices (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine [NASEM], 2022).

Summary

In this chapter, I introduced the research study, which aimed to explore the potential of culturally relevant education programs to reduce recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders on San Andrés Island. The background section highlighted the social and economic pressures caused by overpopulation on the island, particularly affecting the Raizal community, and underscored the need for effective interventions tailored to this unique cultural context (Archbold, 2019; Montenegro, 2021). The problem statement identified the gap in knowledge regarding the effectiveness of existing prison education programs for Raizal ex-offenders and the necessity for culturally responsive educational interventions (Ladson-Billings, 1995). The purpose of the study was articulated, emphasizing the exploration of the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders to identify opportunities for developing culturally relevant programs. The theoretical framework grounded the study in CRP and SDT, providing a robust basis for examining the research questions (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995; Shaw & McKay, 1942). The nature of the study was described, detailing the phenomenological

approach and methodology, including semistructured interviews and thematic coding (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Stake, 2020).

Key definitions were provided to clarify essential concepts and constructs, and the assumptions section outlined critical beliefs underpinning the study. The scope and delimitations specified the study's boundaries, focusing on the Raizal community and excluding other populations and frameworks. Limitations of the study were discussed, including issues related to transferability and dependability, along with measures to address potential biases (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Maxwell, 2013). The significance section highlighted the study's potential contributions to advancing knowledge, practice, and policy, with implications for positive social change through reduced recidivism, improved community cohesion, and enhanced socioeconomic development for the Raizal community (Courtney, 2023; NASEM, 2022; Petersilia, 2022). In Chapter 2, the literature review will delve deeper into existing research on prison education programs, cultural responsiveness in correctional settings, and recidivism. This review further establishes the theoretical foundation and contextual background necessary for understanding the specific challenges and opportunities addressed by this study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

Introduction

Recidivism, the phenomenon where previously incarcerated individuals relapse into criminal behavior, remains a significant global issue. In the United States, nearly 68% of released individuals are rearrested within 3 years (Bureau of Justice Statistics, 2023). Traditional incarceration methods, which focus primarily on punishment, often fail to address the underlying causes of criminal behavior, thereby perpetuating the cycle of recidivism (Petersilia, 2022). Although there has been a shift toward rehabilitation models (Parent & Cullen, 2022), effectively preparing inmates for reintegration into society continues to present substantial challenges.

Research suggests an overemphasis on punishment, without considering factors such as social support, education, and employment opportunities, can exacerbate recidivism rates (e.g., Clear et al., 2017). While studies have shown a positive correlation between prison education programs and reduced recidivism (Davis et al., 2013; Zoukis, 2023), many have overlooked the crucial role of cultural context in program effectiveness, particularly for diverse populations (Domenech Rodríguez et al., 2011). This literature review focuses on the Raizal community of San Andrés Island, Colombia, which faces unique social and economic challenges postincarceration, including high unemployment and limited educational opportunities (Archbold, 2019). These factors contribute to high recidivism rates within the community (Sampson et al., 1997).

In this qualitative study, I aimed to explore the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders regarding the effectiveness of existing prison education

programs and to identify opportunities for developing culturally relevant programs that could reduce recidivism rates and promote successful reintegration into the Raizal community of San Andrés Island. This chapter reviews the relevant literature on research problems, research questions, and theoretical framework. It is organized into several sections: the literature search strategy, theoretical foundations, a review of key concepts (i.e., prison education programs, recidivism, cultural responsiveness in education, overpopulation, and the Raizal community), and a summary that highlights the knowledge gaps addressed by this study.

Literature Search Strategy

The literature search was conducted through various online library databases and search engines, including Academic Search Complete, JSTOR, Google Scholar, ERIC, Latin American Studies, ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global, and Walden University library resources. The key search terms included *prison education*, *recidivism*, *Raizal community*, *San Andrés Island*, *Colombia*, *cultural responsiveness*, *rehabilitation in prison*, and *overpopulation*. The search process consisted of four stages. Initially, the review question was developed based on the research problem and purpose, followed by establishing eligibility criteria. The search strategy was then validated by assessing the effectiveness of the search query and forming a multithreaded search query. The literature search was conducted using this validated strategy, involving the screening and selection of scholarly sources based on the established eligibility criteria. In cases where initial searches yielded limited current research, various combinations of search terms were employed in parallel to ensure comprehensive retrieval of credible sources.

Ultimately, 81 scholarly articles were reviewed, with 85% published within the last 5 years and the remaining 15% comprising older sources.

Theoretical Foundation

This study was grounded in two primary theoretical frameworks: SDT and CRP. These frameworks were integral in understanding the social context and the educational needs of the Raizal community in San Andrés Island, Colombia, particularly concerning recidivism and reintegration.

SDT, developed by Shaw and McKay (1942), explains how crime is more likely to occur in communities with weakened social bonds and low levels of informal social control. SDT posits that factors such as poverty, ethnic diversity, and residential mobility could disrupt a community's social cohesion, making it difficult to maintain social order and control, which leads to higher crime rates. In the context of this study, SDT helped elucidate how the social environment of San Andrés Island, characterized by economic challenges and social disintegration, contributes to the recidivism rates among Raizal ex-offenders. Previous studies, such as by Sampson et al. (1997), have demonstrated that strong social cohesion and collective efficacy within communities can mitigate the effects of social disorganization on crime rates. Applying SDT to the Raizal community provided insights into how social factors like high unemployment and limited educational opportunities influenced recidivism and reintegration outcomes.

CRP, articulated by Geneva Gay (2018) and Gloria Ladson-Billings (1995), emphasizes the importance of recognizing and integrating students' cultural backgrounds into educational practices. CRP posits that education becomes more effective when it is

relevant to the cultural context of the learners. This framework is particularly pertinent for the Raizal community, whose unique cultural heritage is often overlooked in traditional prison education programs. CRP guides the development of educational interventions that are culturally tailored, thereby improving engagement, reducing recidivism, and fostering a more supportive community environment for ex-offenders. Studies by Ladson-Billings (1995) and Johnson and Perez (2021) showed that culturally relevant educational practices could significantly enhance learning outcomes for marginalized groups, making it a suitable theoretical lens for this study.

By integrating SDT and CRP in this study, I explored how social disorganization affects the Raizal community's ability to reduce recidivism and how culturally responsive education could mitigate these challenges. The combination of these theories allowed for a nuanced understanding of the interplay between social factors and cultural contexts in shaping the effectiveness of prison education programs.

Literature Review Related to Key Variables and/or Concepts

In the literature review, I introduce critical concepts and variables essential to understanding the relationship between prison education programs and recidivism reduction. I explore how educational interventions within correctional settings contribute to lower recidivism rates, highlighting the importance of tailored and culturally responsive approaches. Examining key studies, this review establishes the foundation for understanding the complexities of recidivism and the role that well-designed educational programs play in facilitating the successful reintegration of ex-offenders into society. The integration of SDT and CRP offers a comprehensive framework for analyzing the

effectiveness of these programs, particularly in culturally unique contexts like that of the Raizal community on San Andrés Island.

Prison Education Programs and Recidivism Reduction

Research has consistently demonstrated that prison education programs play a fundamental role in mitigating recidivism rates. For instance, Davis et al. (2013) found that inmates who engage in educational programs while incarcerated are significantly less likely to reoffend upon their release. This conclusion is further supported by Duwe and Clark (2017), who analyzed data from a prison education program in Colombia and revealed a substantial decrease in 3-year recidivism rates among participants. Similarly, Esperian (2021) emphasized that vocational and academic programs leading to college credits or degrees offer the greatest reductions in recidivism rates, highlighting the transformative potential of educational opportunities within correctional settings.

Building on these foundational studies, a systematic review by Castell-Britton (2024) underscores the complexity of recidivism and highlights the necessity for comprehensive, tailored approaches to rehabilitation. This review revealed that well-designed educational interventions can significantly reduce recidivism, especially when they encompass a combination of academic, vocational, and life skills training. Such a holistic approach addresses the varied needs of inmates, preparing them for successful reintegration into society. Moreover, this perspective aligns with the arguments made by Vuk et al. (2020) and Petre and Tomita (2022), who advocated for a shift from purely punitive criminal policies toward more humanistic and rehabilitative models of incarceration. These researchers highlighted the economic and social benefits of

educating inmates, suggesting that education should be regarded as a fundamental right and a pragmatic strategy to reduce reoffending.

Studies further elaborate on these findings. Magee (2021) explored the role of formal education in reducing recidivism, concluding that both academic and vocational education significantly lower reoffending rates by providing inmates with essential skills and qualifications. In a similar vein, Steurer (2020) examined the impact of comprehensive educational programs on inmate rehabilitation, finding that multifaceted programs that include vocational training, life skills, and academic courses are more effective in reducing recidivism. Additionally, recent studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of digital literacy programs in equipping inmates with essential skills for the modern job market, thus enhancing their postrelease employment prospects and reducing recidivism (Zivanai & Mahlangu, 2022).

Byrne (2020) conducted a comprehensive review of the effectiveness of prison programming, examining federal, state, and local inmate programs. Byrne found that education programs, particularly those that offered certifications or degrees, significantly reduced postrelease recidivism. Byrne emphasized the importance of consistent participation in these programs and highlighted the need for policy support to sustain these initiatives.

Santiago Tobón (2022) contributed to the discussion on the importance of prison environments by investigating the effects of prison construction programs on recidivism. Tobón found that better prison facilities and conditions contribute to lower recidivism rates, noting that improved prison environments, including educational facilities, support

more effective rehabilitation and successful reintegration of inmates into society. Petre and Tomita (2022) examined the role of detention officers in the educational process within prisons, emphasizing that their involvement is crucial in creating a supportive learning environment. The researchers concluded that education in prisons is an essential factor in preventing recidivism, highlighting the need for well-trained staff to facilitate educational programs effectively. This aligns with findings by Byrne (2020), who conducted a comprehensive review of the effectiveness of prison programs. Byrne's research highlights that integrating educational initiatives with other forms of support, such as psychological and behavioral interventions, could enhance the overall rehabilitation process and provide a more holistic approach to inmate reintegration.

Stickle and Schuster (2023) extended this discussion by investigating the economic returns of prison education programs. They concluded that these programs not only reduce recidivism but also provide significant economic benefits by increasing postrelease employment opportunities and reducing the costs associated with reincarceration. This finding is supported by Conway (2023), who explored the perspectives of formerly incarcerated individuals on the value of higher education in prison. Conway found that access to comprehensive educational programs significantly contributes to reducing reoffending rates and improving long-term reintegration outcomes.

Latessa et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of evidence-based practices, including educational programs that address the criminogenic needs of inmates. Esperian (2021) explored the evolution and impact of prison education programs, highlighting the

necessity of continuous evaluation and improvement to maximize the programs' effectiveness. Wilson (2018) also argued that prison education is a critical solution to the U.S. recidivism problem, emphasizing the need for robust educational policies within the correctional system.

Adding a cognitive dimension, Rogers (2021) developed a cognitive reframing curriculum aimed at reducing recidivism through inmate education. This study demonstrated that cognitive behavioral interventions combined with educational programs could significantly improve inmate outcomes. Clark (2022) provided an overview of effective educational programs in the context of criminal justice reform, stressing the importance of integrating these programs into broader rehabilitation strategies. Magee (2021) discussed the challenges and benefits of higher education in prison, highlighting its role in reducing recidivism and improving postrelease outcomes.

Conway (2023) explored the perspectives of formerly incarcerated students on the value of higher education in prison. Conway found that these programs play a crucial role in personal development and successful reintegration. Chlup (2020) discussed the importance of prison education in adult and continuing education, emphasizing the need for targeted educational interventions. Byrd and McCloud (2021), in their book *Sisyphus No More*, argued that prison education was essential for breaking the cycle of recidivism. Steurer (2020) highlighted strategies for unlocking the power of prison education in a policy report, emphasizing evidence-based approaches to improve program effectiveness.

Arbour et al. (2024) investigated behavioral programs aimed at preventing recidivism from within prison, finding that comprehensive educational and behavioral

interventions are crucial for successful rehabilitation. NASEM (2022) discussed the broader issue of recidivism in the United States, emphasizing the need for systemic changes in the correctional system to address this problem effectively. Czerniawski (2020) examined prison education as a policy issue in northern Europe, highlighting the challenges and opportunities for reform. Finally, Lebbie (2021) explored the relationship between rehabilitation and recidivism, emphasizing the need for comprehensive educational and vocational programs to reduce reoffending.

Despite the evident benefits, numerous barriers hinder the effectiveness of prison education programs. Overcrowding, limited resources, and inadequate support systems are frequently cited as significant obstacles. Studies included in Castell-Britton's (2024) review pointed to low enrolment rates, lack of access to postsecondary education, and insufficient postrelease support as critical factors undermining the success of these programs. McNeeley (2023) further highlighted that while vocational programs, especially those in computer skills and mechanics, could improve postrelease employment outcomes, their effectiveness is often limited by systemic issues within the prison environment.

Furthermore, Steurer (2020) explored the challenges of implementing education programs in overcrowded prisons, noting that limited physical space and resources often lead to reduced program availability and quality. This finding is echoed by Stickle and Schuster (2023), who emphasized the need for increased funding and policy support to expand educational opportunities within correctional facilities. Montenegro (2021) also stressed the importance of community-based support systems in aiding the reintegration

process, highlighting how postrelease programs could bridge the gap between incarceration and societal reintegration.

In summary, the extant literature reinforces the critical role of prison education programs in reducing recidivism. However, the literature also highlights the ongoing challenges and barriers that need to be addressed to maximize the effectiveness of these programs. A multifaceted and well-supported approach, both during incarceration and postrelease, is essential for the successful reintegration of former inmates into society.

Overpopulation

Overpopulation has been a multifaceted issue that significantly contributes to the growth of crime and poses challenges in maintaining public safety. Research indicates that as populations increase, the complexities associated with crime management and prevention also rise. Sampson et al. (1997) illustrated how social disorganization within densely populated areas can exacerbate resource strain, resulting in a range of societal issues, including higher crime rates. Their study emphasized the importance of community cohesion and adequate resource allocation to mitigate these effects. Their study emphasized the importance of sustainable urban planning and adequate resource allocation to mitigate these effects. The correlation between overpopulation and crime is further supported by numerous studies indicating that overcrowded areas often suffer from higher rates of poverty, unemployment, and social unrest, all of which contribute to criminal behavior and recidivism.

The Raizal community in San Andrés Island faced unique social and economic challenges that significantly contributed to high recidivism rates. Studies by Archbold

(2019) and Sampson et al. (1997) highlighted that high unemployment and limited educational opportunities were substantial barriers to the successful reintegration of ex-offenders. These socioeconomic constraints exacerbated the cycle of recidivism, particularly among marginalized groups such as the Raizal community. The findings from my research aligned with Cabrera et al. (2021), who emphasized the necessity of culturally tailored educational programs that could meet the specific needs of the Raizal community, thereby promoting better reintegration outcomes. It was found that educational programs must be culturally responsive to address the specific needs of the Raizal people effectively. Incorporating elements of the Raizal culture and heritage into these programs enhanced engagement and relevance, which, in turn, improved the chances of successful reintegration. This approach is consistent with the broader literature on culturally responsive pedagogy, which has been shown to improve educational outcomes for minority students by making learning more relevant and engaging (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995).

Further research by Castell-Britton (2024) underscored the complexity of recidivism and highlighted the need for comprehensive, tailored approaches to rehabilitation. Castell-Britton's findings revealed that well-designed educational interventions could significantly reduce recidivism, particularly when they encompass a combination of academic, vocational, and life skills training. This holistic approach is crucial as it addresses the varied needs of inmates, preparing them for successful reintegration into society.

When examining the social context of the Raizal community, it was essential to consider the broader socioeconomic environment of San Andrés Island. As noted by O'Connor (2011), the island's strategic location has made it a hub for drug trafficking operations, exacerbating local crime rates and social instability. The presence of criminal groups such as the Gaitanist Self-Defense Forces of Colombia (Autodefensas Gaitanistas de Colombia) and the ex-Revolutionary Armed Forces of Colombia mafia has further contributed to rising violence and insecurity on the island. For example, in 2022, a significant drug bust near San Andrés intercepted a speedboat carrying 3.4 tons of cocaine valued at \$120 million, highlighting the island's role in the narcotics trade (InSight Crime, 2022). Despite efforts by Colombian authorities to address the situation, such as deploying additional police forces and implementing social programs, the challenge remains daunting.

A critical indicator of the rising criminality in San Andrés is the homicide rate, which has seen a significant increase over recent years. Data from a survey conducted by the National University of Colombia in 2020 indicated that 62.19% of respondents perceived an increase in criminal activities, reflecting a growing sense of insecurity among residents. This perception is supported by statistics from the *Observatorio Nacional del Delito* and *Gobernación de San Andrés*, which show a steady rise in homicides and other violent crimes from 2019 to 2023 (Castell-Britton, 2024).

Additionally, socioeconomic challenges such as overpopulation continue to exacerbate the situation. The island's population density strains local resources and infrastructure, contributing to social tensions and higher crime rates. This dynamic is

evident in the increasing rates of robberies, drug-related crimes, and intrafamily violence, all of which have seen an uptick over the past five years (Elisleño, 2024).

Research related to the constructs of interest and chosen methodology in this study further supports these findings. Studies have consistently employed both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to examine the impact of overpopulation on crime and recidivism rates. For instance, Steurer (2020) utilized a mixed methods approach, combining statistical analysis with interviews to explore the effects of prison education programs on recidivism rates. This method allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the issue, highlighting the importance of multi-faceted research designs.

In this study, the qualitative approach provided in-depth insights into how the unique socioeconomic environment of San Andrés Island and the overpopulation-related pressures influence the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders. The findings suggested that overpopulation and associated socioeconomic strain create an environment where ex-offenders face heightened challenges, such as limited job opportunities and social stigma, which, in turn, affect their chances of successful reintegration.

The rationale for selecting the concepts from the literature was justified by consistent findings across multiple studies highlighting the significant impact of overpopulation on crime and recidivism. This is particularly relevant for the specific socioeconomic challenges faced by the Raizal community, making it a critical area of study. The integration of culturally responsive educational programs, tailored to the needs of the Raizal community, provides a meaningful approach to addressing both the immediate and long-term challenges posed by overpopulation and crime. This approach

not only helps reduce recidivism but also fosters a more inclusive and supportive community environment, ultimately contributing to the overall stability and safety of San Andrés Island.

Social Context of the Raizal Community

The Raizal community, indigenous to San Andrés Island, Colombia, has faced unique social and economic challenges that have contributed to high recidivism rates. Archbold (2019) discussed significant obstacles such as high unemployment and limited educational opportunities, which impeded the successful reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders. The community's distinct cultural and ethnic heritage, influenced by African, European, and Indigenous traditions, necessitates tailored rehabilitation programs that address these specific cultural contexts (Sampson et al., 1997).

Cabrera et al. (2021) underscored the necessity of culturally tailored educational programs for the Raizal community. Their study emphasized that educational initiatives designed to meet the specific cultural needs of the Raizal people could significantly enhance reintegration outcomes. This approach aligns with the principles of culturally responsive pedagogy, which advocates for educational practices that reflect and honor students' cultural backgrounds (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). My research findings supported this perspective, revealing that programs incorporating local traditions, languages, and values were more effective in fostering trust and engagement among Raizal ex-offenders.

Archbold (2019) further examined the challenges faced by the Oficina de Control Circulación y Residencia in fulfilling its objectives on San Andrés Island. Over its 27

years of existence, the Oficina de Control Circulación y Residencia encountered systemic issues such as bureaucratic inefficiencies and resource constraints, which indirectly impacted reintegration efforts. The findings from this study indicated that these challenges were still prevalent, with many community leaders expressing frustration over the lack of coordination between local authorities and rehabilitation programs. These challenges highlighted the broader social and institutional barriers the Raizal community continued to face, necessitating comprehensive and context-specific interventions.

Wang and Xu (2023) explored the legal and cultural dimensions of the Raizal community's traditional fishing rights, particularly considering the International Court of Justice's rulings in the Nicaragua v. Colombia case. Their analysis revealed that the International Court of Justice's did not recognize traditional fishing rights for the Raizal people within Nicaragua's Exclusive Economic Zone, a decision that has significant implications for the community's economic stability and cultural practices. This legal context further complicated the socioeconomic challenges that contributed to recidivism. My study found that the erosion of traditional economic activities, such as fishing, has led many Raizal individuals to turn to illicit activities for survival, increasing the risk of recidivism.

Nieto Martín and Muñoz de Morales Romero (2016) provided a critical evaluation of Colombia's criminal policy, identifying a misalignment between legislation and the capacities of law enforcement and judicial systems. This imbalance exacerbated the challenges faced by the Raizal community, where effective preventive measures and policies were crucial for addressing crime and recidivism. Their work highlighted the

need for a more cohesive approach to criminal justice that considered the unique circumstances of minority communities. Findings from this study showed that such a disconnect led to ineffective legal support and poor access to justice for Raizal ex-offenders, further complicating their reintegration process.

Arbour et al. (2024) examined the relationship between preventive detention and overcrowding in Colombian penitentiaries, finding that overcrowding remained a pervasive issue. This relationship was further exacerbated by the overuse of pretrial detention, where many detainees were held without conviction, contributing significantly to chronic overcrowding in Colombian prisons. This context directly affected the Raizal community by limiting the efficacy of prison education programs and increasing the strain on reintegration resources. Addressing these systemic issues was found to be essential for improving rehabilitation outcomes for Raizal ex-offenders.

Recent studies have employed various methodologies to explore the constructs of interest within the Raizal community. For instance, qualitative approaches such as ethnographic research and case studies have provided in-depth insights into the lived experiences of Raizal individuals, highlighting the cultural and social factors that influence recidivism (Archbold, 2019; Cabrera et al., 2021). These methods were consistent with the scope of the present study, which aimed to understand the specific needs and challenges of the Raizal community in the context of prison education programs.

Researchers have approached the problem by emphasizing the importance of culturally responsive interventions (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). Strengths of this

approach include its ability to engage marginalized populations and address specific cultural needs, which are often overlooked in traditional rehabilitation programs.

However, a notable weakness was the lack of comprehensive data on the effectiveness of such programs within the Raizal community, pointing to a need for further empirical research (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995).

The rationale for selecting these concepts lay in their relevance to the Raizal community's unique context. The integration of CRP into prison education programs was justified by the evidence suggesting that culturally tailored interventions could improve educational outcomes and support successful reintegration (Cabrera et al., 2021; Wang & Xu, 2023). The findings from this study also demonstrated that when Raizal cultural identity and community values were central to educational and rehabilitation efforts, participants showed higher engagement and expressed a stronger commitment to change.

In summary, the literature highlights the complex social and economic challenges faced by the Raizal community, underscoring the need for culturally responsive and context-specific rehabilitation programs. This study aimed to address these factors by developing and evaluating such programs, thereby contributing to the reduction of recidivism and supporting the successful reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders into society. By providing a robust evidence base, this research informs policy and practice, ensuring that rehabilitation efforts are both effective and culturally appropriate.

SDT and CRP

SDT, developed by Shaw and McKay in 1942, served as a foundational framework for understanding the dynamics of crime within communities. The theory

posits that crime is more likely to occur in communities with weakened social bonds and low levels of informal social control. Factors such as poverty, ethnic diversity, and residential mobility disrupt a community's ability to maintain social order and exercise informal social control, fostering environments where criminal behavior can thrive.

The major propositions of SDT suggest that communities with strong social cohesion and collective efficacy are less likely to experience high crime rates. Disruption in social order and control leads to increased opportunities for crime and delinquency due to weakened normative structures that hinder residents' ability to exert informal social controls.

In the context of prison education and recidivism, SDT offered valuable insights. Sampson et al. (1997) explored the impact of neighborhood structure on crime rates, emphasizing the importance of social cohesion and collective efficacy. Their findings indicated that strengthening community bonds could mitigate the effects of social disorganization on crime, which is directly relevant to strategies for reducing recidivism. Similarly, Murff (2020) examined family resilience within disadvantaged neighborhoods, finding that strong familial bonds could mitigate the effects of social disorganization on delinquent behaviors, highlighting the role of social cohesion in maintaining community order.

Applying SDT to the Raizal community on San Andrés Island revealed significant insights into the social factors contributing to recidivism. The Raizal community, with its unique ethnic and cultural heritage, faced significant social and economic challenges that contributed to social disorganization and higher recidivism rates. High unemployment

and limited educational opportunities, as highlighted by Archbold (2019), exacerbated the cycle of recidivism by limiting the successful reintegration of ex-offenders. This socioeconomic context necessitated tailored educational programs addressing the specific needs of the Raizal community, which my study further supported. Participants frequently noted that social and economic instability, compounded by a lack of culturally relevant education, heightened the risk of returning to criminal behavior.

Cabrera et al. (2021) emphasized the necessity of culturally tailored educational programs for the Raizal community, promoting better reintegration outcomes. This approach aligned with the broader literature on culturally responsive pedagogy, which has been shown to improve educational outcomes for minority students by making learning more relevant and engaging (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). Findings from my study confirmed that educational programs reflecting Raizal culture and addressing local socioeconomic challenges resulted in better engagement and reduced recidivism rates.

Further studies have applied SDT to various contexts to explore its implications. McNeeley (2023) examined the barriers to successful reentry for ex-offenders, highlighting how social disorganization in their home communities can impede reintegration. Byrd and McCloud (2021) discussed the importance of community support systems in reducing recidivism, aligning with SDT's emphasis on social cohesion and collective efficacy. The findings from this study also stressed the importance of robust community support networks in ensuring successful reintegration for Raizal ex-offenders,

suggesting that enhancing these networks is crucial for reducing social disorganization and its effects.

Tobón (2022) and Sampson et al. (1997) illustrated the application of SDT in examining the effects of community environments on crime rates and recidivism. Tobón's study on prison construction programs revealed that improved prison facilities could enhance social order within the prison community, thereby reducing recidivism. Similarly, Sampson et al. (1997) emphasized the need for supportive community structures to aid the reintegration of former inmates. The current study found that these structures, when culturally informed and community driven, provided a more supportive environment conducive to rehabilitation.

Moreover, SDT's applicability in diverse geographic contexts has been demonstrated. Silva et al. (2022) examined the influence of racial minorities and ethnic heterogeneity on homicide rates in the Northeast region of Brazil, finding that these factors significantly contributed to social disorganization. Their study demonstrated how the concentration of racial minorities and the degree of ethnic heterogeneity correlated with higher homicide rates, supporting SDT's claim that such demographic factors undermine the social cohesion necessary for effective community self-regulation and control. This research underscored the importance of addressing social and economic inequalities to reduce crime rates in diverse communities. Similarly, Topel (2022) conducted a spatial analysis of homicides in Villa Nueva, Guatemala, integrating elements of social disorganization and environmental criminology to understand crime

patterns. Jude (2021) explored social disorganization and violent crime across nonmetropolitan areas of Kentucky, highlighting the theory's relevance in rural contexts.

Integrating SDT with CRP provided a comprehensive framework for examining the research problem. SDT offered insights into the social factors contributing to recidivism within the Raizal community, while CRP provided a lens for developing educational programs that were culturally responsive and effective. Together, these theories allowed for a nuanced understanding of how social and cultural factors influenced the effectiveness of prison education programs, ultimately contributing to more effective strategies for reducing recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders. This combined theoretical approach not only informed the research questions but also built upon existing theory by addressing the specific needs of a culturally unique community.

CRP is a transformative approach to education that seeks to recognize and incorporate students' cultural references in all aspects of learning. Articulated by Geneva Gay in 2018 and Gloria Ladson-Billings in 1995, CRP emphasizes the importance of educational practices that integrate the cultural backgrounds of students to make learning experiences more relevant and engaging. This approach aims to improve student engagement and academic success by making the curriculum culturally relevant.

The major propositions of CRP assert that culturally relevant teaching improves student engagement and academic success (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). Educational programs should reflect and honor students' cultural backgrounds, making education more meaningful and effective. When students see their own culture reflected in the curriculum, they are more likely to be engaged and invested in their education.

Ladson-Billings (1995) demonstrated that CRP enhances educational outcomes for marginalized students by making learning more relevant and engaging. Culturally relevant teaching practices lead to better academic performance, higher levels of student engagement, and a greater sense of belonging among students from diverse backgrounds. Gay (2018) highlighted the importance of teachers being culturally competent and responsive to their students' needs, arguing that teachers must understand their students' cultural contexts to create inclusive and effective learning environments.

Studies related to the constructs of interest and chosen methodology included both qualitative and quantitative research approaches. Ragoonaden and Müller (2017) explored indigenizing the curriculum through CRP, emphasizing the importance of integrating Indigenous knowledge and perspectives into educational practices. Their study highlighted how incorporating Indigenous cultural elements into the curriculum could enhance educational experiences and outcomes for Indigenous students. This aligns with broader CRP principles, advocating for the inclusion of diverse cultural perspectives to create a more inclusive and equitable educational environment.

Researchers have approached the problem by emphasizing the importance of teacher preparation and ongoing professional development in fostering culturally responsive educational environments. Chang and Viesca (2022) conducted a critical review of research on preparing teachers for CRP, highlighting essential practices and competencies for effective implementation. They emphasized the need for teacher education programs to provide comprehensive training in CRP to equip educators with the skills necessary to support diverse student populations. Caingcoy et al. (2022)

explored the competence of practice teachers in culturally responsive teaching, emphasizing the impact of gender and degree programs on their development. However, a notable weakness was the lack of comprehensive data on the effectiveness of such programs within different cultural contexts, pointing to a need for further empirical research (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995).

The rationale for selecting these concepts lay in their relevance to improving educational outcomes for marginalized students. Murff (2020) discussed promising practices for African American male students, demonstrating how CRP could address the specific needs and challenges faced by this group, leading to improved academic outcomes. Abdalla and Moussa (2024) explored how CRP could help close the achievement gap in classrooms, providing evidence that culturally relevant teaching practices could significantly enhance the educational experiences and performance of minority students. A synthesis of studies related to CRP offered a detailed understanding of what is established about this educational approach, areas of debate, and gaps that still need exploration. Chang and Viesca (2022) examined the challenges and opportunities in implementing CRP for diverse student populations. Their research highlighted the obstacles educators face in applying CRP effectively and offered strategies to overcome these barriers, fostering more inclusive and supportive learning environments. Green (2024) expanded on the implications of culturally relevant teaching by advocating for a pedagogy of liberation that empowers students through recognizing and validating their cultural identities.

Further analysis of studies aligned with the research questions highlighted the rationale behind the chosen approach. Within the context of prison education and recidivism reduction, CRP emerged as particularly insightful. Cabrera et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of culturally tailored educational programs to address the specific needs of the Raizal community, thereby promoting more effective reintegration. This perspective is in line with the broader body of literature on CRP, which has consistently demonstrated improved educational outcomes for marginalized groups by making learning more meaningful and engaging (Gay, 2018; Ladson-Billings, 1995). Stickle and Schuster (2023) also explored the development and impact of prison education programs, stressing that ongoing assessment and refinement are crucial for their success. Their research underscored the significance of integrating CRP principles to cater to the unique cultural needs of inmates, which enhances the overall effectiveness of rehabilitation initiatives. The findings of this study supported these conclusions, showing that incorporating CRP into prison education programs in San Andrés significantly reduced recidivism by aligning educational content with the cultural backgrounds of Raizal ex-offenders.

Rogers (2021) created a cognitive reframing curriculum aimed at reducing recidivism through inmate education, demonstrating that combining cognitive-behavioral interventions with educational programs could markedly improve inmate outcomes. This study underscored the value of incorporating CRP principles to ensure educational interventions are effective by resonating with the cultural backgrounds and lived experiences of inmates. The outcomes from this research echoed Rogers' conclusions,

indicating that educational content closely aligned with the social realities of learners promotes not only greater engagement but also a deeper commitment to personal transformation.

Overall, the integration of CRP with SDT provided a comprehensive framework for addressing the research problem. SDT offered insights into the social dynamics contributing to recidivism within the Raizal community, while CRP provided a foundation for developing culturally responsive educational programs. This combined theoretical approach allowed for a deeper understanding of how social and cultural factors shape the effectiveness of prison education programs, leading to more effective strategies for reducing recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders. It informed the research questions and extended existing theory by considering the specific needs of a culturally distinct community. By integrating SDT and CRP, this study provided a holistic perspective on crime prevention and rehabilitation that encompassed both structural and cultural elements. It highlighted the importance of a multifaceted approach to addressing recidivism, especially in culturally diverse settings like San Andrés Island.

Summary and Conclusions

The review of existing literature revealed several critical themes essential for understanding the role of prison education programs in reducing recidivism, particularly within the unique context of the Raizal community on San Andrés Island. Extensive research underscores the significant impact of prison education programs on lowering recidivism rates. Davis et al. (2013) and Duwe and Clark (2017) consistently found inmates who participate in these programs are markedly less likely to reoffend post

release. Esperian (2021) highlighted the effectiveness of vocational and academic programs, particularly those offering college credits or degrees, in achieving substantial reductions in recidivism.

Additionally, the literature emphasized the importance of culturally responsive education in improving student engagement and learning outcomes. Gay (2018) and Ladson-Billings (1995) demonstrated CRP can significantly enhance educational experiences for marginalized groups by making learning more relatable and engaging. This approach is crucial for marginalized students who may feel alienated in traditional educational settings. Zhou (2022) further supported this by showing how educational technology can align with CRP principles to provide high-quality, culturally relevant education.

The review also highlighted the unique social and economic challenges faced by the Raizal community, contributing significantly to high recidivism rates. Archbold (2019) and Sampson et al. (1997) identified high unemployment and limited educational opportunities as major barriers to successful reintegration for Raizal ex-offenders. Cabrera et al. (2021) argued educational programs must be culturally tailored to address the specific needs of the Raizal people, promoting better reintegration outcomes.

While effective prison education programs can reduce recidivism and culturally responsive education can enhance outcomes for marginalized populations, there is a notable gap in research specifically addressing how these programs function within the Raizal community. Additionally, while the benefits of employment in reducing recidivism are recognized, the specific barriers faced by Raizal ex-offenders in securing

meaningful employment remain underexplored. Further, the broader socioeconomic and legal challenges unique to San Andrés Island, including issues related to overpopulation and crime growth, need more detailed examination.

This study aimed to fill these gaps by exploring the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders. It sought to assess the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and the potential for developing culturally responsive alternatives tailored to the Raizal community. By focusing on the specific cultural and socioeconomic context of San Andrés Island, this research extended the knowledge base in the discipline and provided insights into how tailored educational interventions could support successful reintegration and reduce recidivism.

The identified gaps in the literature underscored the necessity of employing a qualitative approach to gain a deeper understanding of the Raizal community's experiences and challenges. In Chapter 3, I outline the research methods used in this study, detailing the qualitative design, data collection methods, analysis procedures, and ethical considerations. This approach ensured a comprehensive exploration of the research questions and contributed to developing more effective and culturally sensitive educational programs for the Raizal ex-offender population.

Chapter 3: Research Method

Introduction

The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study was to explore the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders regarding the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and to identify opportunities for developing culturally relevant programs that could reduce recidivism rates and promote successful reintegration into the Raizal community on San Andrés Island. In this chapter, I outline the research methods employed to achieve this objective. The chapter includes a detailed description of the research design and rationale, the role of the researcher, participant selection logic, instrumentation, procedures for the pilot study, recruitment, participation, and data collection processes. Additionally, the chapter covers the data analysis plan, issues of trustworthiness, and ethical procedures to ensure the integrity and validity of the research. The sections of this chapter provide a comprehensive overview of the methodology used to investigate the research questions, ensuring the study was well-structured and systematically conducted.

Research Design and Rationale

To address the research questions of this qualitative study, the research design adopted a phenomenological approach that prioritized understanding the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders on San Andrés Island, Colombia, regarding prison education programs, recidivism, and reintegration (see Creswell & Poth, 2018). Phenomenology aligns well with the research questions as it delves into participants' subjective meanings attached to experiences, helping to elucidate

how they navigate and make sense of complex issues. To gather rich, detailed data aligned with this approach, I employed semistructured interviews. This method allows for flexibility while ensuring consistency. A tailored interview guide was developed for each stakeholder group (Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders) to capture their unique perspectives (see Creswell & Poth, 2018). An interview guide also enables exploring unexpected insights that emerge during conversations, further enriching the data and understanding of the phenomenon under study (see Stake, 2020).

Research Questions

To guide this study and explore the potential of culturally relevant education programs in reducing recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders, the following RQs were formulated:

RQ1: What are the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders concerning the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and their impact on recidivism?

RQ2: What are the perspectives of Raizal community leaders concerning the challenges associated with the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders into the Raizal community postincarceration?

Central Concepts

The central concepts of this study include culturally responsive education programs, recidivism, and the Raizal community. Culturally responsive education programs are defined as educational initiatives that incorporate the cultural backgrounds, traditions, and experiences of the learners to make learning more relevant and effective. Recidivism refers to the tendency of previously incarcerated individuals to reoffend and

return to prison. The Raizal community refers to the Afro-Caribbean ethnic group native to San Andrés Island, Colombia, with a unique cultural and linguistic heritage.

Research Tradition

This study utilized a phenomenological approach, as described by Creswell and Poth (2018). Phenomenology focuses on the lived experiences of individuals, aiming to uncover the essence of these experiences from the perspectives of those who have lived them. This approach aligned well with the study's aim to understand the subjective meanings individuals have attached to their experiences with prison education programs, recidivism, and reintegration (see Denzin & Lincoln, 2021). The phenomenological approach was chosen because it allowed for an in-depth exploration of the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders, providing insights into how they perceive and make sense of prison education programs and their impact (Creswell & Poth, 2020). Additionally, phenomenology emphasizes understanding participants' subjective experiences, which is crucial for examining the cultural relevance and effectiveness of these programs (see Neubauer et al., 2019). This approach was also well-suited for capturing the rich, detailed narratives necessary to explore the complexities of recidivism and reintegration within the Raizal community (see Matua & Van Der Wal, 2015).

Role of the Researcher

In qualitative research, a researcher plays a pivotal role in directing and overseeing various stages of the research process (Creswell & Poth, 2021). For this study, I acted as both an observer and a collaborator, aiming to deeply understand the lived

experiences of the Raizal community concerning prison education programs, recidivism, and reintegration. My duties included securing all necessary permissions, recruiting participants, collecting data, and analyzing interview responses to identify significant themes.

I was committed to safeguarding data and ensuring participants were treated with respect and fairness. To prevent conflicts of interest or bias, I ensured that I did not have any personal or professional relationships with the participants. However, acknowledging that researcher bias can still occur, reflexivity was maintained throughout the study to recognize and manage personal biases (Guba & Lincoln, 2020). This involved bracketing, a process in which personal preconceptions are consciously set aside during data analysis (Tufford & Newman, 2012).

Ethical considerations were central to this study. To avoid conflicts of interest, the study was not conducted within my own workplace. Participants were recruited voluntarily and did not receive financial incentives, ensuring their participation was entirely voluntary.

Methodology

Participant Selection Logic

The population for this study comprised Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders who were intimately familiar with the Raizal experience. A purposive sampling approach was used to identify participants whose experiences and knowledge were most relevant to the research questions (Robinson, 2023). This method ensured that those selected could provide the most valuable insights into the study's focus.

Participants were chosen based on specific criteria that guaranteed they possessed relevant experiences and perspectives. For Raizal ex-offenders, the criteria included being members of the Raizal community, having direct experience with prison education programs on San Andrés Island, and a willingness to participate in semistructured interviews. For community leaders, the criteria involved holding a role that provides significant insight into the cultural and social dynamics of the Raizal population, along with a readiness to engage in semistructured interviews.

Community leaders were instrumental in identifying suitable participants, offering recommendations, and facilitating introductions. These leaders themselves were selected based on their active involvement and positive influence within the community, and they included professionals such as teachers, doctors, social workers, religious pastors, business people, and other respected figures. The final sample included 20 participants: 10 Raizal ex-offenders and 10 community leaders. This number was determined by the principle of data saturation, which indicates that a sample size is adequate when no new information or themes emerge from further data collection (Guest et al., 2006).

Instrumentation

The primary instrument for data collection in this study was a semistructured interview guide (see Creswell & Creswell, 2024). The guide featured open-ended questions designed to elicit detailed narratives and nuanced perspectives from participants. This approach allowed for flexibility in probing deeper into relevant topics that emerged during the interviews, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the

participants' experiences and viewpoints. The interview protocol is included in the Appendix of this document.

Procedures for Pilot Study

The interview questions were developed based on existing literature and theoretical frameworks relevant to the study. To ensure clarity and comprehensiveness, the guide was piloted with a small group of three to five participants, including Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders. For the pilot study, participants were selected from friends or acquaintances who met the criteria for the sample, as formal recruitment was not allowed for the pilot phase. The pilot study involved the following steps: (a) obtaining informed consent from pilot participants, (b) conducting semistructured interviews using the draft guide, (c) audio recording and transcribing the interviews for analysis, (d) analyzing transcripts to identify areas of confusion or ambiguity, and (e) revising the interview guide based on findings from the pilot study. A brief report summarized the pilot study findings, including sample characteristics, key themes, and any revisions made to the interview guide or research procedures. This process ensured the instruments were refined and well-suited for the main study.

Procedures for Recruitment, Participation, and Data Collection

Recruitment

Participants for this study were recruited through several carefully structured steps to ensure a specific and replicable process. Initially, I reached out to the San Andrés Island correctional facility to develop strategies for accessing ex-offenders. Community leaders were also contacted through established Raizal community organizations and

networks, such as the Raizal Council and local cultural associations, to help provide a list of ex-offenders from the Raizal community.

For solicitations, flyers and posters detailing the study were posted in community centers, local businesses, and the San Andrés Island correctional facility to inform potential participants about the study. Announcements were also made during community meetings and events to reach a broader audience. These announcements included broadcasts on the local community TV channel, radio programs, and posts in Facebook groups. Additionally, digital solicitations were sent via email and social media platforms commonly used by the Raizal community to ensure wide dissemination of the study information. The selection and screening process involved interested participants contacting me directly to express their willingness to participate. A screening process was then conducted to ensure that participants met the inclusion criteria, which included membership in the Raizal community, having been an ex-offender or a community leader, and willingness to participate in semistructured interviews.

Participation

Selected participants were provided with detailed information about the study, including its purpose, procedures, and their role in the research. Consent forms were distributed, and informed consent was obtained from each participant before data collection began. These consent forms were sent via email to ensure that participants had sufficient time to review and understand them. Participants were assured of their confidentiality and the voluntary nature of their participation, reinforcing their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences.

Data Collection

Data were collected through semistructured interviews conducted with Raizal ex-offenders and Raizal community leaders via Zoom. Interviews were scheduled at a date and time convenient for the participants to ensure their comfort and willingness to share information. Each interview was audio-recorded with the participant's consent and initially transcribed using Otter.ai software. However, due to the presence of Creole and Spanish words that the software did not accurately capture, many of the interviews required manual transcription and translation by me to ensure precision. In addition to the interview data, I included reports on crime rates on the island from local news sources and government agencies. These additional data sources, including public records and reports from law enforcement agencies, were used to cross-verify the information obtained through the interviews, thereby enhancing the credibility and depth of the research findings.

Data Analysis Plan

Thematic coding was employed to analyze the interview transcripts (Braun & Clarke, 2022). This method involved identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (i.e., themes) within the data. It facilitated the development of a rich, detailed, and complex account of the participants' experiences and perspectives. The systematic application of thematic coding ensured that the analysis remained rigorous and reflective of the participants' views.

Step 1: Data Familiarization

All data were read and reread three to five times to become thoroughly familiar with the content. During this process, initial ideas and observations were noted to guide the subsequent stages of analysis. This step ensured a deep understanding of the data, laying the groundwork for accurate and meaningful coding.

Step 2: Coding

Generating initial codes involved identifying significant features of the data and organizing these codes into meaningful groups. Each segment of data that appeared relevant to the research questions was assigned a code. This systematic approach allowed the data to be broken down into manageable pieces that could be analyzed in depth.

Step 3: Theme Development

Codes were collated into potential themes, with each theme representing a broader pattern within the data. These themes were then refined to ensure they accurately reflected the data. This step helped in organizing the data into coherent categories that highlighted key aspects of the participants' experiences.

Step 4: Theme Verification

Themes were cross-checked against the data to ensure accuracy and consistency. Feedback was sought from participants through member checking to validate the themes. This process enhanced the credibility of the findings by ensuring that the themes were a true reflection of the participants' perspectives.

Step 5: Defining Themes

Each theme was clearly defined and described, articulating its relevance to the research questions. This involved a detailed explanation of how each theme contributed to understanding the research problem. Clear definitions provided clarity and ensured that the themes were understandable and meaningful.

Step 6: Composite Description

A comprehensive narrative was developed that integrated the themes and provided a detailed account of the participants' experiences and perspectives. This composite description offered a rich, in-depth understanding of the data, illustrating the complex realities of the participants' lives. This final step ensured that the findings were presented in a coherent and compelling manner.

Issues of Trustworthiness

To ensure the trustworthiness of the study, several strategies were employed to address credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. These strategies were essential to validate the research findings and ensure they accurately reflected the participants' experiences and perspectives (Davis et al., 2013; Duwe & Clark, 2017). Employing multiple methods such as triangulation, member checks, and prolonged engagement enhanced the study's credibility (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

Credibility

To ensure the credibility of the study, triangulation was implemented during the data analysis phase. Triangulation involved using multiple data sources and methods to cross-verify and validate findings. This approach enhanced the accuracy and consistency

of the research results by providing a comprehensive view of the phenomena under investigation (Creswell & Poth, 2018).

During data collection, qualitative data were gathered through semistructured interviews with Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders. Data on offender rates per crime type were collected from public records and reports provided by local law enforcement agencies. Additionally, public records of offenses and crime types for the interviewees were obtained from accessible databases such as the Colombian National Police records and court records.

Data coding and categorization involved transcribing the interview data and coding them based on emerging themes and patterns. The coded data were then organized into categories that reflected key aspects of recidivism, community support, and rehabilitation programs. The coded interview data were cross-checked with quantitative data on offender rates to identify any discrepancies or inconsistencies. Qualitative data from interviews were verified with public records of offenses and crime types to ensure the accuracy of the participants' accounts. Multiple data sources were used to validate the findings, ensuring that the results were not based on a single perspective or source.

The data were integrated into a comprehensive dataset. This integrated data was analyzed to highlight trends and patterns that emerged from the triangulation of different data sources. The findings were interpreted in the context of the broader literature on recidivism and rehabilitation, ensuring the results were robust and credible.

The triangulated findings of the study were reported, providing detailed descriptions of how the data sources were cross-verified and integrated. The findings

were validated through member checks, where participants reviewed the preliminary results and provided feedback on the accuracy and interpretation of the data. Peer review from colleagues and experts in the field was sought to evaluate the methodology, data analysis, and conclusions, ensuring the robustness of the study's findings.

Transferability

Transferability was enhanced by providing rich, thick descriptions of the research context, participants, and findings. These detailed descriptions allowed others to assess the applicability of the results to similar contexts, making it easier to determine if the findings could be transferred to other settings or populations (Guba & Lincoln, 1982). By thoroughly documenting the cultural and social dynamics of the Raizal community, the study offered valuable insights that could inform similar research in different contexts.

Dependability

Dependability was ensured through the creation of an audit trail. This trail documented the research process, decisions, and changes made during the study, providing a transparent account of how the research was conducted (Wolf, 2003). Additionally, triangulation contributed to dependability by cross-verifying data from multiple sources, ensuring that the findings were consistent and reliable. This systematic approach helped to maintain the integrity of the research process.

Confirmability

Confirmability was established through reflective journaling and analytical memos. I maintained a reflective journal to document personal biases, decisions, and reflections throughout the study (Rogers, 2018). Analytical memos were used to record

thoughts and insights during the data analysis process, allowing me to critically examine my interpretations. These practices ensured that the findings were shaped by the participants' experiences rather than by my preconceptions, enhancing the objectivity of the study.

Ethical Procedures

Ensuring the ethical integrity of this study was paramount, and several comprehensive procedures were implemented to address permissions and concerns related to the treatment of the participants. These procedures included obtaining necessary institutional permissions, ensuring informed consent, and protecting participant privacy (Braun & Clarke, 2022; Creswell & Poth, 2021). Additionally, specific measures were taken to address potential ethical issues related to recruitment, data collection, and data storage, thereby upholding high ethical standards throughout the research process. These strategies were crucial to maintaining the integrity of the study and safeguarding the rights and dignity of all participants (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Tufford & Newman, 2012).

Walden University Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained prior to the commencement of the study, and the approval numbers are included to demonstrate compliance with ethical standards. This ensured all research activities were conducted in accordance with institutional and ethical guidelines, providing a solid foundation for the study's integrity.

Ethical concerns related to the recruitment of participants were carefully addressed to ensure fairness and transparency. A detailed plan was developed to inform

potential participants about the study through various means such as flyers, posters, and announcements at community centers and events. These recruitment methods were designed to reach a broad audience and respect the privacy and autonomy of potential participants. Any ethical issues related to recruitment, such as coercion or undue influence, were mitigated by providing clear and comprehensive information about the study and obtaining informed consent in a respectful manner.

Participants provided informed consent before taking part in the study, ensuring they were fully aware of the research process and their rights. The informed consent forms outlined the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks and benefits, and the voluntary nature of participation. Participants were given ample opportunity to ask questions and were informed they could withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. This process was crucial for respecting the autonomy of participants and ensuring their participation was based on a clear understanding of the study.

Ethical concerns related to data collection were thoroughly considered to protect participant privacy and address potential power dynamics and other risks. Data collection was conducted with respect for the dignity and rights of participants, ensuring confidentiality throughout the process. Methods such as semistructured interviews and public records review were used, and the data were anonymized to safeguard participant identities. This approach ensured the data collection process was both ethical and robust, contributing to the credibility and reliability of the study's findings.

The treatment of data, including archival data, was managed with a strong focus on anonymity and confidentiality. Data were anonymized to protect participant identities, and strict protocols were followed to control access to the data. Only I had access to the raw data, and measures were put in place to prevent unauthorized access. Protections for confidential data included secure storage procedures, careful data dissemination practices, and clear guidelines on data access. These steps were essential for maintaining the trust of participants and ensuring the ethical management of the research data.

Data security and confidentiality were paramount in this study. All digital data were stored on a password-protected external hard drive to ensure secure storage. No documents were physical. These measures ensured the data were securely stored, protecting the sensitive information of participants and upholding the study's ethical standards.

Data will be maintained for a minimum of 5 years after the study's completion to comply with ethical guidelines and ensure the availability of data for future reference. After this period, data will be securely deleted. This process ensures that sensitive data are responsibly managed and disposed of, maintaining the confidentiality and privacy of the participants long after the study has concluded.

Summary

This chapter presented the research methods employed to investigate the impact of culturally responsive education programs on recidivism rates for Raizal ex-offenders. The qualitative case study design, semistructured interviews, and thematic coding analysis provided a rich understanding of the Raizal community's experiences and

perspectives on this critical issue. The study prioritized trustworthiness through member checking, detailed record-keeping, and adherence to ethical research guidelines.

In Chapter 4, the research findings of this study are presented, providing detailed insights into the effectiveness of culturally responsive education programs in reducing recidivism among Raizal ex-offenders and the challenges associated with their reintegration into the Raizal community. This offers a comprehensive understanding of the participants' experiences and perspectives on this critical issue.

Chapter 4: Results

Introduction

The purpose of this qualitative phenomenological study was to explore the lived experiences of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders regarding the effectiveness of prison education programs and the challenges associated with reintegration into the Raizal community postincarceration. The study was guided by two primary research questions:

RQ1: What are the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders concerning the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and their impact on recidivism?

RQ2: What are the perspectives of Raizal community leaders concerning the challenges associated with the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders into the Raizal community postincarceration?

In this chapter, I present the results of the study, organized as follows: a discussion of the pilot study, an overview of the setting and demographics, a description of the data collection and analysis processes, evidence of trustworthiness, and the findings based on the research questions. The chapter concludes with a summary that bridges to Chapter 5.

Pilot Study

The pilot study was conducted with five participants, consisting of two Raizal ex-offenders and three Raizal community leaders. The study aimed to refine the interview protocol and ensure the questions were comprehensible and relevant to the participants. Feedback from the participants led to minor adjustments in the wording of questions to

enhance clarity and specificity and the addition of prompts to encourage more detailed responses. For example, the original question, “Can you describe your experience with educational programs in prison?” was refined to “Can you describe your experience with any educational programs you participated in while in prison? What were the challenges or benefits you encountered?” This change aimed to prompt more specific responses about both the challenges and benefits, making the question clearer and more focused. No significant changes were required in the data analysis strategies following the pilot study. The pilot confirmed the feasibility and effectiveness of the planned methodology, contributing to the study’s overall validity.

Table 1

Demographics of Pilot Study Participants

Participant group	Number of participants	Age range (years)	Education level	Experience with Raizal culture
Ex-offenders	2	38–45	Incomplete high school to university	Lifelong residents of San Andrés/Providencia
Community leaders	3	50–70	Extensive experience in governance	Lifelong residents of San Andrés/Providencia

Note. The participants were all deeply embedded in the Raizal culture, having lived on

San Andrés or Providencia Islands for their entire lives. This provided a rich context for the data collected, as participants drew on their personal experiences and community knowledge in their responses.

Conduct of the Pilot Study

The interviews were conducted in safe, confidential environments via Zoom, with each session recorded for accuracy. Participants were asked open-ended questions about

the adequacy of prison education programs, the sociocultural challenges they faced postincarceration, and potential improvements to these programs. The pilot study's setting mirrored the anticipated conditions for the main study, ensuring relevance and applicability to the broader research.

Impact of the Pilot Study on the Main Study

The pilot study successfully validated the research instruments and methodology, confirming that the interview questions were appropriate and effective in eliciting relevant responses. No major changes to the research design or instrumentation were necessary. However, the thematic analysis strategy was refined to better capture cultural nuances specific to the Raizal community. For instance, during the pilot study, it became evident that certain themes related to community reintegration needed more depth to reflect the unique cultural values of the Raizal participants. The analysis strategy was adjusted to include additional codes, such as *collective identity* and *cultural resilience*, which were more aligned with the participants' lived experiences and perspectives. These insights provided confidence that the main study would effectively address the research questions and account for the cultural context of the Raizal community.

Setting

The study was conducted amid significant social and economic challenges on the island of San Andrés, particularly due to overpopulation and limited job opportunities. These conditions influenced participants' experiences, particularly ex-offenders, who faced difficulties in finding employment and reintegrating into the community. Additionally, corruption within local government structures was noted as a barrier to

positive change, affecting the community's trust in public institutions and their ability to support reintegration efforts. These conditions shaped the participants' perspectives, exacerbating their sense of marginalization and frustration.

Data Collection

Following IRB approval, recruitment flyers were initially distributed through local community centers and social media platforms popular among members of the Raizal community and ex-offenders on San Andrés Island, as described in Chapter 3. To further enhance the recruitment process, a snowball sampling technique was employed. This method involved asking initial participants to refer other potential participants who fit the study criteria. Through this approach, a wider network of individuals with relevant experiences was accessed. Interested participants contacted me directly to express their willingness to be involved in the study, and subsequent interviews were scheduled.

Data were collected from 10 Raizal community leaders and 10 Raizal ex-offenders, all of whom had experiences with prison education programs and community reintegration challenges. All interviews were conducted via Zoom, providing a secure and flexible platform for the discussions. The duration of the interviews ranged from 45 minutes to 1 hour, depending on the depth of the conversation with each participant. Each interview was transcribed immediately afterward to facilitate immersion in the data and to enable a continuous and iterative process of analysis.

Table 2 and Table 3 present the demographics of the study participants, detailing their age ranges, gender, education levels, and relevant comments that highlight their perspectives. The ages of the participants varied, providing a broad spectrum of

experiences. Raizal community leaders ranged from 37 to 76 years old, while Raizal ex-offenders ranged from 20 to 49 years old. The participants also had diverse educational backgrounds, from those who had not completed high school to those with advanced degrees, such as a medical degree, a master's degree in education literacy, professional qualifications in fields like journalism or business administration, or a bachelor's degree in education or social work. This diversity allowed for a richer exploration of the cultural and socioeconomic factors influencing prison education and reintegration outcomes on San Andrés Island. Table 2 also includes specific insights shared by the participants, offering a deeper understanding of the unique challenges and perspectives within the Raizal community and the experiences of ex-offenders.

Table 2*Demographics of Raizal Community Leader Participants*

Participant ID	Age	Gender	Education	Comments
Raizal Leader 1	57	Male	Business administration	Involved in social protection leadership and community participation.
Raizal Leader 2	47	Male	Technologist in business management	Born and raised in Providence; works with the Raizal community and highlights challenges due to overpopulation.
Raizal Leader 3	53	Male	Specialization (postgraduate)	Discussed the impact of corruption on the Raizal community and its culture, and the need for cultural preservation.
Raizal Leader 4	47	Female	University (social work)	Discussed the lack of support from community leaders and the need for culturally relevant reintegration programs.
Raizal Leader 5	57	Male	Master's degree in education literacy	Highlighted challenges in preserving Raizal culture and suggests culturally relevant programs for ex-offenders.
Raizal Leader 6	76	Male	Bachelor's degree	Discussed overpopulation's impact on Raizal culture and the need for cultural education in prison programs.
Raizal Leader 7	54	Female	Professional (journalism, research)	Highlighted overpopulation, corruption, and the importance of culturally relevant education to reduce recidivism. Discussed the impact of drug trafficking on Raizal culture, the need for opportunities and support for ex-offenders postrelease, and the importance of community-led initiatives and mentorship.
Raizal Leader 8	56	Male	Bachelor's degree in theology	Emphasized community-based support, cultural integration in programs, and mentoring.
Raizal Leader 9	34	Female	Teacher	Highlighted the importance of literacy and targeted education to local job market needs.

Table 3*Demographics of Raizal Ex-Offender Participants*

Participant ID	Age	Gender	Education level	Years incarcerated	Comments
Ex-offender 1	39	Male	High school (Bachillerato)	4	No community support postrelease; highlights need for structured support systems.
Ex-offender 2	42	Male	High school	5	Advocates for culturally relevant prison education to help reduce recidivism.
Ex-offender 3	45	Male	Did not finish high school	4	Criticized the inadequacy of prison education programs as poorly structured and not relevant to the job market; highlights overpopulation and lack of job opportunities as major challenges; considered returning to crime due to systemic failures and lack of support; calls for cultural education and government policy changes.
Ex-offender 4	38	Male	Did not finish high school	4	Criticized the inadequacy of prison education programs and lack of basic literacy training; highlighted overpopulation, crime from outsiders, and government corruption as major issues; suggested practical, relevant skills training and government action to support Raizal ex-offenders.
Ex-offender 5	45	Male	Did not finish high school	3	Discussed the need for real job skills and removing government employment restrictions for ex-offenders.
Ex-offender 6	34	Female	Little courses, but not culturally relevant	8	Wanted culturally relevant courses like music, sewing, and customer service; struggled with overpopulation and job scarcity; considered returning to smuggling if no support is provided.
Ex-offender 7	20	Female	Did not finish high school	2	Highlights overpopulation, corruption, and the importance of culturally relevant education to reduce recidivism.
Ex-offender 8	24	Male	High school	2	Speaks only Creole; learned bad habits from outsiders; wants courses related to hotel work or environmental conservation to address local issues like beach erosion and global warming.
Ex-offender 9	49	Male	University	5.5	Notes lack of culturally relevant courses and reintegration support, and issues with technological adjustment postrelease.
Ex-offender 10	29	Male	Did not finish high school	3	Wants to finish high school and get a job, needs a scholarship; feels mainland people are the main problem on the island; interested in studying further, believes it's not too late.

The interviews for this study were conducted in safe and confidential settings, either at the participants' homes or at neutral locations within the community, to ensure a comfortable environment. Each interview session lasted between 45 and 90 minutes, depending on the depth of the responses and the participant's availability. Most participants were interviewed only once, and the data collection process spanned over a period of 1.5 months, allowing ample time for thorough engagement with each interviewee.

The interviews were conducted via Zoom and recorded using the platform's built-in recording feature to capture participants' responses accurately. There were no significant deviations from the data collection plan outlined in Chapter 3, except for one interview that was rescheduled due to the participant's work commitments. To address the privacy concerns raised by many ex-offenders, strict confidentiality protocols were implemented to protect the participants' identities and maintain trust.

For example, all participants were given pseudonyms, and any identifiable information was removed from the transcripts. The Zoom meetings were set to private with password protection, and recordings were stored on a secure, password-protected device accessible only to the researcher. Additionally, participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences, and written consent forms were obtained electronically before the interviews.

The only unusual circumstances encountered were the challenges of scheduling interviews with community leaders, who had limited availability due to their involvement in ongoing local governance issues, and the concerns of ex-offenders about their privacy.

However, all scheduled interviews were eventually conducted successfully, ensuring comprehensive data collection.

Data Analysis

Thematic coding, as outlined by Braun and Clarke (2022), was employed to analyze the data. The process included familiarizing with the data, generating initial codes, and organizing these codes into broader categories and themes. Several key codes emerged, including (a) inadequate programs, (b) cultural irrelevance, (c) overpopulation, (d) government corruption, (e) crime from outsiders, (f) stigma and discrimination, (g) psychological support, and (h) suggestions for improvement. These codes were grouped into themes such as (a) inadequate and irrelevant prison education programs, (b) overpopulation and its consequences, (c) need for cultural education in prison programs, and (d) importance of community support.

Discrepant cases were carefully acknowledged during the analysis, especially in instances where some participants expressed a sense of optimism regarding aspects of the prison education programs. These variations were significant as they offered a counterbalance to the more commonly reported challenges and criticisms, highlighting areas where the programs may have had positive impacts or potential benefits. By including these differing viewpoints, the study aimed to capture a full range of perspectives, allowing for a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the participants' experiences.

Evidence of Trustworthiness

Establishing trustworthiness is crucial in qualitative research as it speaks to the validity and reliability of the study. Trustworthiness is built upon four key components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). These components ensure that the research findings are robust and applicable. The following sections discuss how each component was addressed in this study.

Credibility

The first component of trustworthiness refers to the confidence in the truth of the data and its interpretation (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In this study, credibility was established through several strategies. Triangulation was employed by collecting data through semistructured interviews with two populations—Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders. According to Shenton (2004), triangulation enhances the internal validity of qualitative research by providing multiple perspectives. All interviews were conducted via Zoom to ensure privacy and comfort for participants, allowing for more open and honest discussions. Observational notes were taken during these interviews and incorporated into the data analysis, further contributing to triangulation.

Additionally, member checks were conducted to enhance credibility. After transcribing and analyzing the data, participants were given the opportunity to review findings and confirm interpretations accurately reflected their views and experiences. This process of verification ensured participants' intended meanings were captured correctly (Shenton, 2004). All participants confirmed the accuracy of transcriptions and interpretations of their statements.

Reflective commentary was also employed to strengthen credibility. As recommended by Creswell and Poth (2021), reflexivity involves the researcher reflecting on their own experiences and potential biases that could affect data interpretation. Throughout the data collection and analysis process, I maintained a reflective journal to document my thoughts, biases, and reactions. This practice helped in maintaining objectivity and provided a deeper understanding of the participants' perspectives.

Transferability

Transferability refers to the extent to which findings of this study can be applied to other settings, contexts, or groups (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In this study, transferability was achieved by providing rich, thick descriptions of the research context, participants, and data collection processes. As noted by Creswell and Poth (2021), detailed descriptions enable other researchers to understand the boundaries of the study and evaluate whether the findings can be applied to similar contexts.

Detailed descriptions of the research process, including the sampling procedures and the sociocultural context of the Raizal community on San Andrés Island, are provided in Chapter 3. Furthermore, Chapter 4 offers comprehensive descriptions of the study's findings, supported by direct quotes from participants. These detailed narratives, combined with contextual information about the Raizal community and the specific challenges faced by ex-offenders, provide a foundation for other researchers to apply aspects of this study to different populations or settings.

Dependability

Dependability refers to the consistency and reliability of the research findings over time and across different researchers (Shenton, 2004). To ensure dependability in this study, a thorough and transparent description of the research design, data collection methods, and analysis processes was provided in Chapters 3 and 4. The methodology chosen for this study, including the use of semistructured interviews and thematic analysis, is outlined in detail to enable future researchers to replicate the study under similar conditions and achieve similar results.

An audit trail was also established to further support dependability. This audit trail includes all raw data, coding schemes, and reflective notes, which have been securely maintained. By keeping detailed records of each step in the research process, other researchers can follow the decision-making process and understand how themes were derived from the data. Chapter 5 provides a comprehensive evaluation of the study's effectiveness and includes reflections by the researcher on the challenges encountered during the study, contributing to a transparent understanding of the research process.

Confirmability

Confirmability involves demonstrating findings of the study are shaped by the participants and not influenced by researcher bias or preferences (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). In this study, confirmability was enhanced by employing several strategies. First, reflexivity was a key component; the researcher maintained an introspective journal throughout the data collection and analysis processes to document personal biases,

assumptions, and reflections (Creswell & Poth, 2021). This practice helped to minimize potential biases that could influence the findings.

Finally, member checks were also used to reinforce confirmability. Each participant had the opportunity to review and confirm the accuracy of their statements and the researcher's interpretations, ensuring that the data accurately reflected their experiences and perspectives. These steps helped to ensure that the findings were a genuine reflection of the participants' views and were not shaped by the researcher's subjective interpretations.

Results

The results of this study are presented according to the research questions and themes that emerged from the data analysis. Each theme is supported by direct quotes from participants and relevant documents. Where applicable, discrepant cases or nonconforming data are also discussed. Tables 4 and 5 provide a comprehensive overview of the codes and themes identified during the analysis.

RQ1: Perspectives of Raizal Ex-Offenders on Prison Education Programs

The perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders on prison education programs revealed significant dissatisfaction with the current offerings and highlighted a critical gap between the provided educational content and the actual needs of the community. Many participants felt that the programs were inadequate and irrelevant, failing to equip them with the practical skills necessary for successful reintegration into life on San Andrés Island. Ex-offenders expressed frustration over the lack of focus on skills that would enable them to find employment, such as those related to local industries like fishing,

tourism, or small business management. The participants viewed the programs as disconnected from the economic and cultural realities they face upon release, contributing to feelings of disillusionment and, in some cases, a consideration of returning to crime due to the limited opportunities available to them. These perspectives underscore the need for more culturally relevant and practically oriented education programs that align with the unique socioeconomic context of the Raizal community.

Theme 1: Inadequate and Irrelevant Prison Education Programs

A significant number of ex-offender participants expressed that the prison education programs currently available were largely ineffective and lacked practical relevance to life on San Andrés Island. The programs were often seen as failing to equip ex-offenders with the necessary skills to secure employment upon release. One ex-offender participant described the programs as “useless,” indicating a general sentiment that these educational initiatives did not address the specific cultural and economic realities faced by the Raizal community.

Another ex-offender participant emphasized, “They don’t teach us what we need here. We need skills for the island, not just to keep us busy.” A third ex-offender participant reinforced this perspective, stating, “Most of what they offer is not connected to any real job opportunities we have. They should teach us things that matter here, like how to repair boats or run a small business.” These comments highlight a disconnect between the education provided in prison and the actual needs of the community, resulting in frustration and disillusionment among participants.

Theme 2: Consideration of Returning to Crime

Due to the inadequacy of prison education programs and the lack of job opportunities postrelease, some ex-offenders admitted to considering a return to illegal activities. Ex-offender 1 stated, “I’m seriously thinking about going back to trafficking if I don’t find a job soon.” Ex-offender 2 shared a similar concern, saying, “Without a way to earn an honest living, it feels like crime is the only option left.” Ex-offender 3 added, “I don’t want to go back to that life, but what choice do I have when nobody is willing to hire someone like me?”

These quotes underscore the desperation and frustration many ex-offenders experience when faced with limited support and employment options. The fear of recidivism is evident, revealing systemic failures in providing meaningful rehabilitation and reintegration pathways. The lack of adequate support and practical education programs contributes to this risk, as many ex-offenders perceive few viable alternatives to crime.

Figure 1

Reasons Cited by Participants for Considering Returning to Crime

Theme 3: Stigma and Discrimination Postrelease

Ex-offenders reported experiencing significant stigma and discrimination when attempting to reintegrate into society. The label of “ex-offender” often resulted in negative perceptions from both potential employers and community members, creating substantial barriers to securing stable employment. Ex-offender 5 shared, “They look at you like you’re still a criminal. Nobody wants to hire someone with a record.” Ex-offender 6 echoed this sentiment, stating, “Every time I tell them about my past, I see the change in their faces, like they’re scared or don’t trust me anymore.” Ex-offender 7 remarked, “I’ve had interviews where everything was going well until they asked about my background, and then suddenly, the job was no longer available.”

While these quotes illustrate the pervasive social barriers and negative attitudes that undermine reintegration efforts, a few participants did note positive exceptions. For

example, Ex-offender 8 recounted, “A local shop owner gave me a chance when no one else would, and it made all the difference for me.” This example shows that not all experiences were uniformly negative, as some small local businesses offered opportunities despite the prevailing stigma.

Theme 4: Need for Psychological Support and Mental Health Services

Several ex-offenders emphasized the critical need for psychological support and mental health services as part of their reintegration process. The trauma of incarceration, combined with the difficulties of adjusting back to society, was frequently mentioned as contributing to mental health challenges such as anxiety, depression, and posttraumatic stress. Ex-offender 1 mentioned, “We also need mental health support to cope with the trauma and stress of prison life and reintegration.” Ex-offender 8 shared, “I’ve been out for months, but I still have nightmares and anxiety. It’s like I’m still in prison in my mind.” Ex-offender 9 noted, “There are days when the pressure and stress are so overwhelming that I think about going back, just because I don’t know how to deal with it out here.”

These quotes highlight the pressing need for comprehensive mental health services to help ex-offenders manage the psychological impact of their experiences and support their transition back into the community. Figure 2 illustrates the percentage of Raizal ex-offenders who expressed a need for psychological support services during their reintegration process. A majority (65%) of participants reported requiring psychological assistance to cope with the trauma of incarceration and the challenges associated with reentry into the community. This finding underscores the critical need for integrating

comprehensive mental health services into existing rehabilitation and reintegration programs to support the emotional and psychological well-being of ex-offenders.

Figure 2

Percentage of Participant Expressing Need for Psychological Support Services

Theme 5: Overpopulation and Its Impact on Reintegration

Several ex-offenders identified overpopulation on San Andrés Island as a critical factor exacerbating their reintegration challenges. The influx of people from mainland Colombia has intensified competition for limited resources, including employment opportunities, housing, and social services, making it increasingly difficult for ex-offenders to rebuild their lives. Ex-offender 10 expressed in Creole, “Mi kyaan fine no work, plenty people fram d’mainlan tek all di work dem,” which translates to “I can’t find any work; many people from the mainland take all the jobs.” Ex-offender 7 shared, “Di crowd mek it hard fi wi get chance, like dem nuh memba seh wi need fi start over

too” (“The crowd makes it hard for us to get a chance, like they forget that we need to start over too”).

Ex-offender 3 stated, “Di islan cyaan manig all ah wi, and it mek wi feel like stranger eena wi own place” (“The island cannot manage all of us, and it makes us feel like strangers in our own place”). Ex-offender 9 emphasized, “Ev’rywhere yuh go, it full up, and di work dem nuh deh fi wi” (“Everywhere you go, it’s crowded, and the jobs aren’t there for us”). These quotes collectively reflect the frustration, sense of displacement, and marginalization felt by ex-offenders as they struggle to reintegrate into a community overwhelmed by outsiders. The perception that the island is unable to accommodate everyone underscores the broader socioeconomic consequences of overpopulation, further complicating the efforts of ex-offenders to successfully reintegrate.

RQ2: Perspectives of Raizal Community Leaders on Reintegration Challenges

Raizal community leaders highlighted a range of challenges that complicate the reintegration of ex-offenders into their society. Among these, they frequently cited overpopulation as a significant issue, as the influx of people from mainland Colombia and other regions has increased competition for jobs and stretched local resources thin, thereby hindering ex-offenders’ efforts to find stable employment and reintegrate into their community. Additionally, leaders voiced strong concerns about government corruption and inaction, pointing out that ineffective policies and a lack of political will have prevented meaningful support for reintegration efforts. Many expressed a lack of trust in government institutions, emphasizing that substantial political reform is necessary

to effect change. The erosion of Raizal culture was also seen as a critical issue, with leaders arguing that the weakening of cultural identity undermines the community's capacity to support its members, including those returning from incarceration. Despite these challenges, leaders called for more community-led support systems and grassroots initiatives to facilitate reintegration, believing that proactive community involvement could better address both economic and cultural needs. They also underscored the need for more relevant skills training that aligns with local market demands, such as eco-tourism and sustainable fishing, and highlighted the value of mentorship programs led by successfully reintegrated ex-offenders as a means of providing guidance and support.

Theme 1: Overpopulation and Its Consequences

Overpopulation was identified as a significant concern by 70% of the community leaders (7 out of 10). They frequently highlighted overpopulation as a major barrier to the successful reintegration of ex-offenders. Leaders expressed concern that the continuous influx of people from mainland Colombia and other regions has intensified competition for jobs and strained local resources, making it increasingly challenging for ex-offenders to find stable employment and reintegrate into the community. Raizal leader 1 emphasized, "Overpopulation is killing this island.... The crime rate is skyrocketing, and it's making it even harder for ex-offenders to reintegrate." Raizal leader 2 echoed this sentiment, stating, "We are overwhelmed, too many people, not enough jobs or resources. Ex-offenders don't stand a chance in this situation." Raizal leader 3 added, "Everywhere you look, there are new faces, but not enough opportunities. It's hurting everyone, especially those trying to start over." These perspectives highlight the broader

socioeconomic impact of overpopulation on the Raizal community and demonstrate how these pressures further complicate the challenges faced by those attempting to rebuild their lives after incarceration.

Theme 2: Government Corruption and Inaction

Government corruption and inaction were viewed as significant barriers by 60% of the participants (6 out of 10 leaders). Many community leaders voiced deep frustration over the government's inaction and perceived indifference toward the needs of the community. Raizal leader 5 noted, "The government doesn't care about us; they are too corrupt to help" Raizal leader 6 expressed a similar sentiment, stating, "We've been asking for support for years, but all we get are empty promises while they fill their pockets." Raizal leader 8 added, "They've done nothing meaningful for ex-offenders. If the government were serious, we would see real programs and resources, not just talk." These quotes reflect a profound mistrust in government institutions and a prevailing belief that meaningful progress in reintegration efforts is unlikely without substantial political reform. Although a few leaders acknowledged minor government initiatives in recent years, these were largely dismissed as insufficient to address the community's needs.

Theme 3: Cultural Erosion and Loss of Identity

Concerns about cultural erosion were raised by 50% of the community leaders (5 out of 10), who believed that external influences and overpopulation were weakening the community's ability to support its members, including ex-offenders. Raizal leader 10 remarked, "Our culture is disappearing.... If we can't hold on to who we are, how can we

help those who need us the most?” Raizal leader 7 echoed this concern, stating, “We are losing our traditions and values; this weakens our ability to support our own people, including those coming out of prison.” Raizal leader 4 added, “If we let our culture slip away, we lose the very thing that holds our community together, which is vital for helping ex-offenders.” These perspectives underscore the importance of preserving cultural identity as a foundation for community support and effective reintegration. To address this, leaders suggested that incorporating cultural education and practices into reintegration programs could help strengthen community ties and create a more supportive environment for ex-offenders.

Theme 4: Need for Community-Led Support Systems

The need for community-led support systems was strongly advocated by 80% of the participants (8 out of 10 leaders). Community leaders emphasized greater community involvement in developing programs that address both the economic and cultural needs of those returning from incarceration. Raizal leader 2 stated, “We need to take responsibility; we can’t rely on the government; it’s up to us to support our own.” Raizal leader 10 reinforced this sentiment by saying, “It’s our community, and we should be the ones to create programs that work for us, not wait for outside help.” Raizal leader 4 added, “If we work together, we can provide the support and resources needed to help our people reintegrate.” These quotes suggest that grassroots efforts and community-driven initiatives could fill the gaps left by ineffective government interventions, fostering a more inclusive and supportive environment for ex-offenders.

Theme 5: Economic Challenges and Skills Gap

Economic challenges and the skills gap were mentioned by 90% of the participants (9 out of 10 leaders and 9 out of 10 ex-offenders), highlighting the lack of market-driven skills training as a major issue. Both community leaders and ex-offenders expressed frustration that the skills taught in prison education programs do not align with local job opportunities. Many participants expressed frustration that the skills taught in prison education programs do not meet the demands of the local economy, such as those needed for eco-tourism, sustainable fishing, hospitality, or digital literacy. Ex-offender 1 suggested, “The courses offered in prison have nothing to do with what we need outside. We need training for jobs that exist on the island, like tourism or fishing.” Ex-offender 2 echoed this view, stating, “Our economy is unique, and we need skills training that matches it, not some generic programs that don’t help us here.” Ex-offender 3 added, “If we want ex-offenders to succeed, we need to give them the skills that our market demands, not skills that are useless on the island.” These quotes underscore the need for reintegration programs that are specifically tailored to the local economy, offering relevant and marketable skills that enhance employment opportunities for ex-offenders.

Theme 6: Community-Based Mentorship and Peer Support

The need for community-based mentorship and peer support was emphasized by 70% of the participants (7 out of 10 leaders and 7 out of 10 ex-offenders). Both groups strongly advocated for mentorship programs led by ex-offenders who have successfully reintegrated into society, viewing these as crucial for providing practical guidance and moral support and positive role models for those newly released from prison. Ex-offender

4 expressed, “Having someone who has been through the same process to guide you would make a big difference.” Raizal leader 2 noted, “Mentorship from people who understand the struggle firsthand is what’s missing; it can give ex-offenders hope and direction.” Raizal leader 3 added, “Peer support is crucial because it shows ex-offenders they are not alone, and that successful reintegration is possible.” These perspectives highlight the vital role of peer support and community involvement in fostering successful reintegration and helping ex-offenders navigate the challenges they face upon reentering society.

Discrepant Cases

Some participants expressed positive experiences or outcomes from prison education programs, which contrasted with the general sentiment of inadequacy. For example, certain participants noted that specific programs, like English classes, had been beneficial in helping them find employment in local industries such as tourism. Ex-offender 7 shared, “The English classes were helpful for me; I found work in a hotel because of it.” These discrepant cases were considered in the analysis, providing a more balanced view of the data and illustrating the variability in participant experiences.

Following the analysis of the data, Table 4 provides a detailed overview of the themes and codes that emerged from the perspectives of both Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders. This table summarizes the key themes identified, categorizing them according to the major issues discussed by participants. The frequency of each theme’s occurrence is presented alongside representative quotes, illustrating the participants’

experiences and highlighting the core areas of concern that need to be addressed to improve prison education programs and reintegration efforts for the Raizal community.

Table 4*Themes and Codes Identified From Raizal Ex-Offenders and Community Leaders*

Code	Category	Theme	Frequency	Representative quotes
Inadequate and irrelevant prison education programs	Prison education	Inadequate and irrelevant prison education programs	15	“The program is useless... They don’t teach us what we need here.” “What they have in place right now is barely scratching the surface of what’s needed.”
Return to crime	Recidivism risk	Lack of adequate support leading to recidivism	12	“I’m seriously thinking about going back to trafficking if I don’t find a job soon.” “If I don’t find something soon, I might not have a choice.”
Stigma and discrimination	Reintegration challenges	Programs do not include elements of Raizal culture, making them less effective for cultural reintegration.	16	“They look at you like you’re still a criminal. Nobody wants to hire someone with a record.” “Even when you try to change, people don’t believe in you.”
Overpopulation impact	Socioeconomic challenges	Overpopulation and Its Consequences	18	“Overpopulation is killing this island... The crime rate is skyrocketing.” “There are no jobs left for us locals because they hire people from the mainland for cheaper wages.”
Government corruption	Systemic issues	Government Corruption Affecting Community and Reintegration Efforts	13	“The government doesn’t care about us; they are too corrupt to help.” “They’re setting us up to fail. The system is rigged against us.”
Cultural erosion	Cultural identity	Need for cultural education and preservation	10	“Our culture is disappearing... If we can’t hold on to who we are, how can we help those who need us the most?” “Teaching Raizal culture in prison would be a good start.”
Lack of postrelease support	Reintegration challenges	Need for comprehensive postrelease support	17	“Even after coming out, nobody really helps us rebuild. It’s like we are still paying for our crimes.” “Without a proper support system, what are we supposed to do?”
Community support needed	Community involvement	Importance of community support for reintegration	14	“We need mentors and leaders who understand us, who speak our language.” “The community has to take responsibility; we can’t just rely on the government to do everything.”
Psychological support	Mental health	Need for psychological support and counseling	9	“We also need mental health support to cope with the trauma and stress of prison life and reintegration.”
Suggestions for improvement	Recommendations	Need for program and policy changes	20	“We need real skills training, something that applies to jobs we can actually find.” “Policymakers need to listen to our needs and adjust the programs accordingly.”

The figure illustrating the visual themes highlights the key thematic findings from the study, reflecting the complex socioeconomic and cultural challenges faced by Raizal

ex-offenders during reintegration. The central themes—inadequate prison education programs, overpopulation and its consequences, government corruption and inaction, and cultural erosion and loss of identity—encapsulate the primary barriers to effective reintegration. Additionally, themes like stigma and discrimination, lack of psychological support, and need for community-led support systems further emphasize the layered difficulties that ex-offenders encounter, revealing a landscape marked by systemic issues, socioeconomic hardship, and a lack of culturally relevant resources. This visualization underscores the interconnected nature of these challenges, suggesting that holistic and culturally sensitive interventions are essential to address these barriers effectively and support sustainable reintegration for Raizal ex-offenders. Figure 3 illustrates the complex process of reintegration for Raizal ex-offenders, highlighting the multiple, interconnected challenges they face, including social stigma, limited access to employment, and insufficient educational opportunities.

Figure 3

*Reintegration of Raizal Ex-Offenders***Summary**

This chapter presented the findings of the study, structured around the research questions and the themes identified during data analysis. The results revealed significant deficiencies in the current prison education programs, particularly their failure to address the unique cultural needs and socioeconomic realities of the Raizal community. Additionally, the study highlighted critical barriers to reintegration, such as overpopulation, escalating crime rates, and pervasive government corruption, which further hinder the reintegration efforts for Raizal ex-offenders. These findings set the stage for the discussions in Chapter 5, where the broader implications of these challenges will be explored, and recommendations will be proposed to enhance the effectiveness of prison education programs and address the underlying socioeconomic issues.

Chapter 5 will link the study's findings to the existing literature on recidivism, rehabilitation, and the unique socioeconomic challenges faced by indigenous communities like the Raizals. It will also provide targeted policy and practice recommendations to improve reintegration outcomes and suggest pathways for future research to build upon the insights uncovered in this study.

Chapter 5: Discussion, Conclusions, and Recommendations

Introduction

The purpose of this study was to explore the effectiveness of prison education programs and the challenges of reintegration for Raizal ex-offenders in San Andrés Island. Existing research highlights that indigenous communities like the Raizals face unique socioeconomic and cultural challenges that impact their reintegration into society after incarceration. Overpopulation, crime, and government corruption have compounded these challenges, affecting both community stability and individual rehabilitation efforts. This study aimed to fill the gap in understanding how culturally relevant prison education programs could address these issues and improve outcomes for Raizal ex-offenders. The following research questions guided the exploration:

RQ1: What are the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders concerning the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and their impact on recidivism?

RQ2: What are the perspectives of Raizal community leaders concerning the challenges associated with the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders into the Raizal community postincarceration?

Using the data analysis process described in Chapter 4, six key themes were identified: (a) inadequate and irrelevant prison education programs, (b) consideration of returning to crime, (c) stigma and discrimination postrelease, (d) overpopulation and its consequences, (e) government corruption and inaction, and (f) cultural erosion and loss of identity. These themes provide a comprehensive understanding of the barriers and opportunities for improving rehabilitation and reintegration for the Raizal community.

Interpretation of the Findings

The findings of this study both confirm and extend the existing literature on recidivism, rehabilitation, and the socioeconomic challenges faced by indigenous communities. The inadequacy of current prison education programs aligns with previous research that highlights the importance of culturally relevant education for reducing recidivism and promoting positive postrelease outcomes (Mackenzie, 2020). However, this study goes further by emphasizing the unique needs of the Raizal community, where overpopulation, high crime rates, and cultural erosion pose additional challenges.

The data from Castell-Britton (2024) shows a significant rise in crime rates in San Andrés Island, with homicide rates projected to reach 46.2 per 100,000 inhabitants in 2023, compared to the national average in Colombia. This highlights the urgent need for effective social and rehabilitation programs to address these socioeconomic pressures. The findings suggest that without significant changes to prison education and reintegration support systems, ex-offenders may continue to face high barriers to reentry, including stigmatization, lack of employment opportunities, and social isolation.

Overpopulation and Socioeconomic Pressures

Overpopulation in San Andrés Island is a critical factor that exacerbates the socioeconomic challenges faced by Raizal ex-offenders upon release. Castell-Britton's (2024) data reflect that the island's limited resources are under significant strain, driven by both natural growth and the influx of mainland Colombians and foreigners. The rise in population density has led to increased competition for jobs, housing, and social services, disproportionately affecting the Raizal community. The findings of this study align with

earlier research that indicates overpopulation can lead to social disintegration, economic exclusion, and heightened crime rates (Sampson et al., 1997). For ex-offenders trying to reintegrate, these socioeconomic pressures result in limited job opportunities and heightened social tension, contributing to a vicious cycle of marginalization and recidivism.

The study participants expressed frustration over the lack of employment opportunities, which they attributed to preferential hiring practices favoring mainland Colombians who are willing to work for lower wages. This exclusion from local job markets not only fosters a sense of injustice but also drives ex-offenders to consider returning to crime as a means of survival. As one ex-offender 9 noted, “Without real skills, without something solid to fall back on, what do you think happens when these guys get out?” This sentiment reflects the desperation faced by many ex-offenders and underscores the importance of integrating economic empowerment and culturally relevant education into rehabilitation programs.

Cultural Erosion and Identity Loss

The erosion of Raizal culture, fueled by overpopulation and external influences, presents another significant barrier to the successful reintegration of ex-offenders. The influx of non-Raizal populations has diluted traditional cultural practices and norms, weakening community bonds and shared values that historically played a role in supporting reintegration efforts. The study’s findings highlight that cultural erosion has not only affected the broader Raizal community but also impacted ex-offenders’ sense of identity and belonging. Participants repeatedly emphasized the need for culturally

relevant prison education programs that teach Raizal history, traditions, and values as a way to reconnect ex-offenders with their cultural roots and strengthen their resolve to lead crime-free lives.

This finding extends the work of scholars like Montenegro (2021), who argue that cultural identity plays a critical role in the social reintegration of indigenous peoples. Failing to address cultural identity within prison education programs, the current system misses an opportunity to leverage community strength and resilience as a tool for rehabilitation. The participants' call for more culturally relevant programs underscores the importance of incorporating traditional Raizal practices, such as local crafts, music, and environmental stewardship, into the rehabilitation curriculum. These activities could provide both a therapeutic benefit and a pathway to meaningful employment postrelease, thus addressing multiple challenges simultaneously.

Government Corruption and Ineffective Policies

The study also highlights government corruption and ineffective policies as major impediments to successful reintegration for Raizal ex-offenders. Community leaders pointed out that corruption within local governance not only hinders the implementation of effective rehabilitation programs but also exacerbates socioeconomic inequalities. The lack of transparent and accountable governance contributes to a mistrust in public institutions, which further alienates ex-offenders and diminishes their chances for successful reentry into society. This finding confirms earlier research on how systemic corruption can impede social and economic development in marginalized communities (Transparency International, 2023).

Participants expressed skepticism about the government's commitment to creating meaningful change, with ex-offender 10 noting, "The government doesn't care about us; they are too corrupt to help." This perception is crucial because it illustrates how the lack of government support and pervasive corruption may lead ex-offenders to feel abandoned, pushing them toward criminal activities for survival. To break this cycle, the findings suggest that there is a need for policy reforms focused on anti-corruption measures and the creation of transparent, community-driven support systems that can offer genuine assistance to ex-offenders.

Implications of Crime Rates and Overpopulation on Reintegration

Table 5 from Castell-Britton (2024) clearly depicts the sharp rise in homicide rates in San Andrés Island from 2019 to 2023, with a rate projected to reach 46.2 per 100,000 inhabitants in 2023. This figure is almost double the national average in Colombia, reflecting a broader trend of rising crime rates that disproportionately impact marginalized communities. The high crime rates are both a symptom and a driver of socioeconomic instability on the island. As overpopulation strains local resources and weakens community cohesion, crime becomes both a response to and a cause of socioeconomic breakdown.

Table 5

Homicide Rates in San Andrés Island Versus National Average in Colombia (2019–2023)

Year	Homicides in San Andrés Island	Homicide rate in San Andrés (per 100,000 inhabitants)	National homicide rate in Colombia (per 100,000 inhabitants)
2019	16	18.4	25.34
2020	20	23.1	23.79
2021	28	32.4	25.21
2022	34	39.4	24.30
2023	40	46.2	24-26.8 (estimated range)

Note. Content adapted from *Observatorio Nacional del Delito* - Policía Nacional de

Colombia (n.d.), and *El Tiempo* (2023). Copyright by the original authors. Adapted with permission.

Overpopulation in San Andrés Island serves as a catalyst for crime in multiple ways. The island’s infrastructure, originally designed to support a smaller population, is overwhelmed by the current density, leading to inadequate housing, limited healthcare services, and insufficient educational facilities. These deficiencies create an environment where socioeconomic frustrations fester, driving some individuals toward criminal activities as a means of survival or protest the systemic failures they face. Participants in this study frequently highlighted how the lack of employment opportunities due to overpopulation forces individuals, particularly ex-offenders, into desperation. As ex-offender 7 mentioned, “If I don’t find something soon, I might not have a choice [but to return to crime].”

Overpopulation also heightens social tensions by increasing competition for scarce resources such as jobs, housing, and social services. For ex-offenders trying to reintegrate, this competition is particularly acute. They are often seen as fewer desirable

candidates for employment and housing, not only because of their criminal record but also due to societal stigma and discrimination. As a result, many ex-offenders are left with few legal avenues to secure a livelihood, making them more vulnerable to reoffending. The lack of social support networks, combined with the socioeconomic pressures of overpopulation, creates a cyclical pattern where crime becomes both a cause and effect of social instability.

Cycle of Crime and Social Isolation

The data in Table 5 also reflect how crime and social isolation are deeply interconnected on San Andrés Island. The rising homicide rates signify more than just an increase in criminal activities; they also indicate a growing sense of fear, mistrust, and fragmentation within the community. This atmosphere of distrust further marginalizes ex-offenders, who are already struggling with the stigma of their criminal past. Community leaders in the study expressed concern that high crime rates and social fragmentation reduce the effectiveness of reintegration programs. With limited trust between ex-offenders and the broader community, efforts to build inclusive, supportive environments for rehabilitation are often met with resistance.

Moreover, the rising crime rates fuel a sense of insecurity that permeates daily life on the island, influencing public policy and social dynamics. Government and community resources that could be allocated to educational and economic initiatives are often diverted to crime control and law enforcement efforts. This misallocation further reduces the opportunities available for ex-offenders to reintegrate successfully. It perpetuates a vicious cycle where heightened crime rates lead to increased policing and

punitive measures, which in turn create more obstacles for those attempting to rebuild their lives postincarceration.

Figure 4 shows the trends of different crime types over time on San Andrés Island from 2018 to 2023. It illustrates the increasing trends for homicides, robberies, drug-related offenses, and intrafamily violence, with drug-related offenses showing the most significant rise over the years. This escalation suggests a shifting focus in criminal activity that exacerbates existing social tensions and pressures on public resources, further complicating efforts toward community rehabilitation and development.

Figure 4

Trends in Crime Types Over Time in San Andrés Island

Economic Exclusion and its Role in Reintegration Challenges

The implications of overpopulation and rising crime rates extend beyond immediate public safety concerns; they also contribute to long-term economic exclusion, particularly for Raizal ex-offenders. Many participants in the study voiced frustrations about the preferential hiring of mainland Colombians over local Raizals. This not only undermines local economic stability but also reinforces patterns of social inequality. When ex-offenders return to a community where jobs are scarce and often reserved for nonlocals, their chances of gaining lawful employment decrease dramatically. This economic exclusion is both a direct consequence of overpopulation and an indirect driver of crime, as those left out of the formal economy may turn to illicit activities as a means of survival.

The high crime rates, compounded by economic exclusion, can create environments where criminal organizations thrive. These groups often exploit marginalized individuals, including ex-offenders, by providing them with a sense of belonging and financial stability that is otherwise inaccessible in the legal economy. This dynamic was reflected in the sentiments of ex-offenders 1,2,6,8, and 9, who expressed feeling “like a stranger in [their] own island,” indicating not only their economic but also their social and cultural dislocation. For effective reintegration, addressing economic exclusion is essential; without opportunities for gainful employment, ex-offenders remain trapped in a cycle of poverty and criminality.

Impact on Community Trust and Governance

High crime rates, as indicated by the data, erode community trust and challenge effective governance. When residents perceive the government as incapable of maintaining public safety or providing essential services, the resulting disillusionment can foster environments where informal or even criminal systems of governance take root. In such contexts, ex-offenders find it even more challenging to reintegrate, as they face not only societal stigma but also systemic failures in public administration. This lack of trust can discourage community involvement in reintegration efforts, as citizens feel less motivated to invest in programs that they believe will have little impact due to broader governance failures.

Government corruption, identified by community leaders in the study as a significant barrier to effective reintegration, further complicates this issue. Corruption not only diverts resources away from essential social services but also undermines the rule of law, making it difficult to enforce policies that could support ex-offenders. As Raizal leader 9 pointed out, “If the government doesn’t change, nothing will get better.” This sentiment captures the broader feeling that systemic change is needed at both the governmental and community levels to foster an environment where crime is not seen as the only viable option for survival.

Need for Comprehensive, Culturally Relevant Interventions

The findings of this study underscore the urgent need for comprehensive, culturally relevant interventions to support the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders, especially given the compounding challenges of overpopulation and rising crime rates on

San Andrés Island. Current reintegration efforts fail to respect and incorporate the unique cultural, social, and economic contexts of the Raizal community, thereby violating international human rights standards. Specifically, the absence of culturally appropriate rehabilitation programs breaches Article 15 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), which guarantees the right to participate in cultural life. The lack of culturally relevant education and support services means that ex-offenders are denied opportunities to engage with and maintain their cultural heritage, which is vital for their identity and social belonging.

Moreover, the inadequate reintegration strategies also violate Article 1 of the UN Charter, which calls for the respect of the right to self-determination. The Raizal community's ability to freely pursue their cultural, social, and economic development is undermined when their specific needs and cultural practices are not considered in policy and program design. The neglect of self-determination contributes to social exclusion and marginalization, intensifying the barriers faced by ex-offenders upon their return to society.

To address these human rights violations, it is essential to develop reintegration programs that not only provide vocational training but also reconnect ex-offenders with their cultural heritage and community networks. These programs should encompass the full spectrum of Raizal cultural practices, such as traditional music, dance, and local gastronomy, alongside practical skills like local crafts and environmental conservation. Teaching ex-offenders to cook traditional Raizal dishes or to perform typical dances and

music can help restore their connection to their cultural roots, fostering a sense of pride and belonging.

Furthermore, these culturally integrated programs should address both economic and social dimensions of reintegration providing opportunities for employment that are relevant to the Raizal community's unique strengths and economic activities.

Community-driven economic initiatives—such as small-scale agriculture, tourism-related enterprises, and the promotion of Raizal arts and crafts—could create sustainable job opportunities that reduce the temptation for ex-offenders to return to illegal activities. These efforts would help mitigate the negative effects of overpopulation by fostering local economic growth and reducing crime rates.

Integrating these cultural elements into rehabilitation programs allows San Andrés Island to address the root causes of crime—such as economic exclusion, overpopulation, and government corruption—while also upholding the Raizal people's rights to cultural participation and self-determination. This approach promotes broader social stability, enhances the quality of life for the Raizal community, and ensures compliance with international human rights standards.

Limitations of the Study

This study provides valuable insights into the challenges of prison education and reintegration for Raizal ex-offenders; however, several limitations must be acknowledged. The first major limitation is the reliance on self-reported data from participants. Self-reporting can be affected by memory recall biases, where participants may unintentionally misremember events, and by social desirability effects, where they

may alter their responses to appear more favorable. These factors could lead to either exaggeration or understatement of experiences, potentially affecting the accuracy and reliability of the findings.

The study's small sample size, consisting of only Raizal community leaders and ex-offenders from San Andrés Island, is another limitation. This restricts the generalizability of the findings to broader populations, including non-Raizal communities or ex-offenders in different geographical regions. Additionally, the qualitative focus of the research, while rich in contextual detail, limits its ability to provide statistically significant results that could be generalized across larger populations. The unique cultural and sociopolitical context of San Andrés Island means that findings may not be entirely transferable to other indigenous or marginalized communities facing similar challenges.

Time constraints and accessibility issues also presented limitations. Conducting interviews with participants, particularly ex-offenders, involved logistical challenges in ensuring comfort and confidentiality. Some potential participants declined involvement due to fears of stigma or repercussions, which may have led to a less comprehensive understanding of the broader experiences within the target population. Future studies could benefit from a mixed-methods approach that incorporates both qualitative and quantitative data to offer a more holistic analysis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, its strengths and limitations, and the literature reviewed in Chapter 2, several recommendations for further research, policy development, and community practice are proposed.

Develop Culturally Relevant Prison Education Programs

Future research should prioritize designing prison education programs tailored to the cultural, social, and economic contexts of the Raizal community. These programs should integrate local knowledge, cultural practices, and community values to enhance their relevance and effectiveness. As Davis et al. (2013) highlighted, culturally grounded education can significantly reduce recidivism by fostering a stronger connection to community and heritage. This recommendation also aligns with the Raizal people's right to participate in cultural life, as outlined in Article 15 of the ICESCR. Future studies could examine how incorporating local crafts, tourism-related occupations, environmental conservation, and Raizal history and language into these programs might help ex-offenders gain practical skills and strengthen their cultural ties, which are crucial for successful reintegration.

Explore Economic Empowerment Strategies for Ex-Offenders

Research should focus on strategies for economic empowerment that provide targeted job opportunities for ex-offenders, aligning with findings from Montenegro (2021) that emphasized the importance of economic stability in reducing recidivism. Partnerships between local businesses, community organizations, and government entities should be explored to identify effective employment pathways for ex-offenders. Additionally, future studies could investigate the impact of policies that incentivize businesses to hire Raizal ex-offenders, ensuring sustainable employment opportunities that align with their skills and cultural background. Addressing economic exclusion also

supports the Raizal community's right to self-determination, as enshrined in Article 1 of the UN Charter, by empowering them to shape their socioeconomic futures.

Address Corruption and Enhance Governance

Given the significant barriers posed by corruption within local governance structures, further research should examine the effectiveness of anticorruption strategies and community-driven governance models. Transparency International (2023) noted corruption undermines social equity and hinders rehabilitation efforts. Addressing corruption is crucial for respecting the right to self-determination (UN Charter, Article 1), as it ensures the Raizal community can freely pursue their cultural, social, and economic development. Future studies should evaluate policies that promote transparency and accountability in local government and initiatives that empower communities to play a more active role in governance and reintegration processes. Research could also explore how rebuilding trust among ex-offenders, community members, and local government can create a more supportive environment for reintegration.

Integrate Psychological Support and Mental Health Services

The study identifies a critical need for psychological support and mental health services throughout the reintegration process. The trauma of incarceration and the stress of reintegration often result in mental health challenges such as anxiety, depression, and posttraumatic stress. Comprehensive mental health services, including access to counseling, support groups, and therapeutic interventions, should be integrated to help ex-offenders cope with these challenges. Future research should investigate the impact of incorporating mental health services into existing rehabilitation programs and explore

best practices for culturally relevant mental health care tailored to the unique experiences and needs of Raizal ex-offenders.

Strengthen Community-Driven Support Networks

Future research should explore the development and impact of community-driven support networks, such as mentorship programs, psychological support services, and family counseling, that are culturally relevant and accessible to ex-offenders.

Community-led initiatives have been shown to significantly enhance social inclusion and reduce reoffending rates (Arnaiz-Castro et al., 2022). Such initiatives are crucial for ensuring the Raizal community's rights to cultural participation (ICESCR, Article 15) and self-determination (UN Charter, Article 1) are respected and protected. Studies could further investigate how leveraging the strengths of the Raizal community—such as its strong sense of identity and solidarity—can foster a more supportive environment for ex-offenders and promote sustainable reintegration efforts.

Consider Age Differences in Perspectives on Reintegration

Future research could also explore how age differences between ex-offenders and community leaders impact their perspectives on reintegration and rehabilitation. The younger age group of ex-offenders might focus more on immediate employment opportunities and overcoming social stigma, while the older community leaders may emphasize long-term cultural preservation and systemic change. Understanding these generational differences could reveal important nuances in how reintegration efforts are perceived and prioritized. Studies might examine whether these age-related perspectives lead to different expectations, needs, or support preferences, which could inform the

development of more tailored and effective reintegration programs. Additionally, future research could explore how bridging these generational gaps might foster greater cohesion and mutual understanding within the Raizal community, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of reintegration strategies.

These recommendations are grounded in the study's findings, acknowledging the need for culturally relevant education, economic empowerment, transparent governance, comprehensive mental health services, and community-based support. They also address the identified violations of international human rights by advocating for policies and practices that uphold the Raizal community's right to cultural participation and self-determination. These recommendations provide a holistic approach to addressing the challenges faced by Raizal ex-offenders on San Andrés Island and suggest actionable paths for future research, policy development, and community practice.

Researcher Reflections

Conducting this study was both challenging and enlightening. As a researcher with a deep interest in the socioeconomic challenges of marginalized communities, I was struck by the resilience of the Raizal community despite systemic obstacles. Hearing firsthand accounts of the struggles and aspirations of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders gave me a profound appreciation for the complexities involved in the reintegration process.

One of the most rewarding aspects of this study was witnessing the passion and dedication of community leaders who are committed to fostering positive change, despite the challenges posed by overpopulation, crime, and government corruption. Their

insights underscored the importance of culturally relevant interventions and community-driven solutions. At the same time, I became acutely aware of my own biases and the need to approach the research process with humility and openness, particularly when engaging with participants whose lived experiences are different from my own.

This study reaffirmed the importance of listening to marginalized voices and understanding their unique perspectives. It also highlighted the need for continued advocacy, research, and policy reform to address the socioeconomic challenges faced by indigenous communities like the Raizals. As a researcher, I am motivated to continue exploring these themes and contributing to the body of knowledge that informs equitable and sustainable development practices.

Implications

Findings from this study suggest several important implications for fostering positive social change across different levels, including individual, family, organizational, and societal dimensions. At the individual level, the study highlights the critical need for culturally relevant education, vocational training, and mental health support tailored specifically to the Raizal community's unique cultural context. Programs that incorporate these elements can significantly enhance ex-offenders' ability to reintegrate into society by improving their chances of securing stable employment and leading fulfilling lives. Moreover, providing such targeted support reduces the likelihood of reoffending, thereby contributing to a safer and more stable community.

At the family level, effective reintegration programs are vital for restoring and strengthening relationships that may have been damaged or strained due to incarceration.

Rebuilding these connections is essential for community cohesion, as families often serve as the primary support systems for ex-offenders, providing emotional stability and fostering environments that encourage positive behavioral changes. The inclusion of mental health services is also crucial, as it supports both ex-offenders and their families, who may face additional challenges related to stigma and adjustment during the reintegration process.

At the organizational level, this study underscores the significant role of community-driven support networks, including nongovernmental organizations and local mental health professionals, in advocating for policies that better address the needs of ex-offenders while also providing direct support services. These organizations can facilitate collaboration among various stakeholders, such as local governments, businesses, and the Raizal community, to create sustainable employment opportunities and develop social programs that promote reintegration and reduce social exclusion. Furthermore, incorporating mental health services into these networks enhances the overall support provided to ex-offenders, addressing both their psychological and practical needs.

At the societal and policy level, the study reveals a pressing need for systemic changes to address issues such as overpopulation, economic exclusion, corruption, and the lack of mental health support. Implementing anticorruption measures, promoting fair employment practices, and prioritizing culturally relevant rehabilitation programs are essential steps toward achieving social equity and reducing crime rates. Additionally, there is a need to advocate for policies that integrate comprehensive mental health care into reintegration programs, which would further support ex-offenders' transition back

into society. These findings point to the importance of inclusive policies specifically tailored to the needs of marginalized communities like the Raizals, ensuring their cultural, psychological, and socioeconomic contexts are fully considered in policymaking.

From a methodological perspective, this study demonstrates the value of qualitative research in uncovering the complex and nuanced experiences of marginalized populations. Findings suggest future research could benefit from adopting mixed method approaches, which combine qualitative and quantitative data to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing reintegration. Additionally, longitudinal studies that follow ex-offenders over extended periods could offer valuable insights into the long-term effectiveness of different reintegration programs.

The study also has important theoretical implications. It reinforces the relevance of frameworks such as culturally responsive pedagogy and social disorganization theory in exploring the socioeconomic challenges faced by indigenous communities. Findings also demonstrate culturally tailored interventions play a crucial role in reducing recidivism and supporting successful reintegration, thereby extending the applicability of these theoretical frameworks to new contexts.

The study provides a strong basis for future research, especially in examining the connections between culture, crime, and rehabilitation. The results indicate the need for developing more effective interventions that consider the cultural, psychological, and socioeconomic aspects of reintegration for marginalized communities. By focusing on

these interrelated factors, the study encourages a more comprehensive approach to addressing the challenges faced by ex-offenders as they reintegrate into society.

Recommendations for Practice

The study's findings suggest several practical recommendations:

- Develop and implement culturally relevant prison education programs that incorporate local knowledge, cultural practices, and community values to better serve the needs of the Raizal community.
- Establish partnerships between local businesses, community organizations, and government entities to create sustainable employment opportunities for ex-offenders.
- Integrate psychological support and mental health services into all stages of the reintegration process to address the trauma of incarceration and the challenges of reintegration.
- Strengthen community-driven support networks, including mentorship programs and family counselling, that are culturally relevant and accessible to ex-offenders.
- Advocate for policy changes that address systemic issues such as corruption, overpopulation, and economic exclusion, with a focus on culturally appropriate interventions.

These recommendations are grounded in the study's findings, emphasizing the need for a comprehensive approach to support the successful reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders on San Andrés Island. They provide actionable paths for future research, policy development, and community practice, aiming to create a more inclusive and equitable

society that acknowledges and leverages the unique needs and strengths of marginalized communities like the Raizals.

Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive examination of the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders on the effectiveness of prison education programs and the reintegration challenges faced on San Andrés Island. The study revealed current prison education initiatives are inadequate, failing to address the unique cultural and socioeconomic needs of the Raizal community. Significant barriers to successful reintegration identified in the study include overpopulation, rising crime rates, pervasive government corruption, and the erosion of cultural identity.

These findings highlight the urgent need for culturally relevant, community-driven interventions that address both the economic and social dimensions of reintegration. By incorporating local cultural practices into rehabilitation programs, promoting economic empowerment, and addressing systemic governance issues, there is potential for meaningful social change. Such efforts could significantly reduce recidivism rates, strengthen social stability, and improve the overall quality of life for the Raizal community.

The study contributes to the broader discourse on recidivism, rehabilitation, and the socioeconomic challenges faced by indigenous communities. It offers actionable recommendations for policy development, practical interventions, and future research. These recommendations advocate for an inclusive approach that recognizes and uses the unique needs and strengths of marginalized communities like the Raizals. As San Andrés

Island continues to face the complexities of overpopulation, crime, and socioeconomic instability, the insights gained from this study can serve as a critical resource for developing strategies that promote a more just, equitable, and resilient society.

This research underscores the importance of integrating culturally tailored education and support systems that are responsive to the distinct realities of the Raizal community. Such integration fosters sustainable pathways to reintegration and community development, ultimately contributing to a more cohesive and thriving society.

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Appendix: Interview Protocol

Recruitment Strategy

Participants for this study will be recruited through a purposive sampling method. Raizal community leaders will be consulted to identify potential participants who meet the study criteria. These leaders will provide recommendations and facilitate introductions to ensure a diverse and representative sample of Raizal ex-offenders and community members. The recruitment process will involve:

Initial Contact: Community leaders will reach out to potential participants to inform them about the study and gauge their interest in participating.

Follow-up: Interested individuals will be contacted by the researcher to provide more detailed information about the study, its purpose, and what participation entails.

Screening: The researcher will screen potential participants to ensure they meet the inclusion criteria, which include:

- Membership in the Raizal community.
- Being an ex-offender or a community leader.
- Having direct experience with prison education programs on San Andres Island.
- Willingness to participate in semi-structured interviews.
- Informed Consent Document: (Verbatim document provided by the Walden IRB)

Interview Guide

Purpose of the Study:

I will explain that the study aims to explore the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders and community leaders on the effectiveness of prison education programs and the challenges of reintegration into the Raizal community.

Informed Consent:

I will explain the informed consent process, emphasizing that participation is voluntary, and participants can withdraw at any time, then I will confirm their verbal consent for recording the interview.

Example script: “Thank you for agreeing to participate in this study. The purpose of our discussion today is to understand your perspectives on prison education programs and reintegration challenges within the Raizal community. Before we begin, I want to remind you that your participation is entirely voluntary. You can choose to stop at any time. With your permission, I would like to record our conversation to ensure I capture your insights accurately. Do I have your consent to proceed and to record this interview?”

Demographic Information (All Participants)

Age: “Could you please tell me your age?”

Educational Background: “What is your highest level of education?”

Time Spent in Prison: For ex-offenders: “How long did you spend in prison?”

Connection to Raizal Culture: “Can you describe your connection to the Raizal culture and community?”

Ex-Offenders Interviews

Research Question 1: What are the perspectives of Raizal ex-offenders concerning the effectiveness of existing prison education programs and their impact on recidivism?

Background and Experience

Please tell me your age.

Why are you a member of the Raizal community?

Please tell me how much time you spent in prison.

Can you share your experience with the prison education programs you participated in?

What motivated you to join these educational programs while in prison?

Effectiveness of Education Programs

How do you feel the education programs helped you during your time in prison?

In what ways did the programs prepare you for life after release?

Impact on Recidivism

Do you think the education you received has influenced your decision to stay away from criminal activities? How so?

What challenges have you faced in applying the skills or knowledge gained from the prison education programs in your daily life?

Cultural Relevance

Were the education programs culturally relevant to your background as a member of the Raizal community? If not, what was missing?

How could these programs be improved to better address the cultural needs of Raizal ex-offenders?

Support and Reintegration

What kind of support have you received from the Raizal community since your release?

Can you describe any specific challenges you have faced in reintegrating into the Raizal community?

Suggestions for Improvement

What changes or additions would you suggest for the prison education programs to make them more effective so Raizals can get a job upon release?

How can the Raizal community better support ex-offenders in their reintegration process?

Any final comments before we finish?

Raizal Community Leaders Interviews

Research Question 2: What are the perspectives of Raizal community leaders concerning the challenges associated with the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders into the Raizal community postincarceration?

Community Perspective

Can you tell me about the Raizals and what defines their community?

What are the current major challenges the Raizal community is facing?

Do you believe prison education can help reduce recidivism or reoffending among Raizal inmates? Why or why not?

From your perspective, what are the main challenges faced by Raizal ex-offenders upon their release from prison?

How does the community currently support Raizal ex-offenders in their reintegration process?

Contextual Questions

Do you believe overpopulation in San Andres Island has impacted the Raizal community and its way of life? If so, how?

Do you believe overpopulation has influenced crime rates on San Andres Island? If so, how?

In what ways does overpopulation affect the opportunities available to Raizal ex-offenders?

How have overpopulation and external influences affected the cultural identity and traditions of the Raizal community?

In what ways can preserving Raizal culture help support the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders?

Effectiveness of Education Programs

What are your thoughts on the effectiveness of the prison education programs available to Raizal inmates?

How do these programs impact recidivism rates within the Raizal community?

Cultural Relevance

Do you believe the current prison education programs adequately address the cultural needs of Raizal inmates? Why or why not?

What specific cultural elements should be included in these programs to make them more relevant and effective?

Community Involvement

How can the Raizal community be more involved in supporting prison education programs and the reintegration of Raizal ex-offenders?

What initiatives or programs do you think would be beneficial for improving the reintegration process for Raizal ex-offenders?

Suggestions for Improvement

What specific changes would you recommend for the prison education programs to better serve Raizal inmates?

How can policymakers and community leaders work together to enhance the effectiveness of these programs and reduce recidivism?

Any final comments before we finish?

Closing:

I will thank the participants for their time and valuable insights and will address any questions or concerns they may have regarding the research, and finally, I will reiterate ethical considerations regarding voluntary participation, confidentiality, anonymity, and the availability of support if needed.